

**A PROJECT REPORT ON
L.P.G./METAL SENSING INTELLIGENT
ROBOT USING BLUETOOTH**

**BACHELOR OF TECHNOLOGY
IN
ELECTRONICS & COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING**

BY

MANU MITRA

05J85A0401

**DEPT. OF ELECTRONICS & COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING
P.INDRA REDDY MEMORIAL ENGINEERING COLLEGE
AFFILIATED TO JNT UNIVERSITY
CHEVELLA, R.R. Dist.
2007-2008**

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INTERNAL GUIDE

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EXTERNAL GUIDE

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2007-2008

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project work entitled "L.P.G./METAL SENSING INTELLIGENT ROBOT USING BLUETOOTH" has been done by

MANU MITRA (05J85A0401)

For partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of degree in Bachelor of Electronics and Communications Engineering affiliated to J.N.T.U.

Guide

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CERTIFICATE OF PROJECT COMPLETION

This is to certify that the following students of **P.Indra Reddy Memorial Engineering College, Chevella, R.R.Dist., Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering** have successfully completed their final year project titled **"Intelligent Gas/Metal Sensing Bluetooth Robot"** in our center. Their attendance and performance was good.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr.Manu Mitra** student of B.Tech., (ECE) Final year at **P.Indra Reddy Memorial Engineering College, Chevella, R.R.Dist.**, has successfully completed his project work in **MIC Tech Center (A division of MIC Electronics Ltd)** during the period 09th January 2008 to 03rd April 2008.

He has completed the project work titled "**Intelligent Gas/Metal Sensing Bluetooth Robot**". The application is developed by using Micro controller (Philips 89C51RDXX) interface, Stepper Motors, Serial Communication, Drivers Circuit Interfacing, IRSensor, Metal/Gas Detector, LCD and Bluetooth Module.

The project was completed to our satisfaction and he has shown keen interest and dedicated to the project during the above period. We place our appreciation for his best efforts.

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Acknowledgement

This successful completion of this Project involves many people.

*We are extremely grateful to our internal guide Kum. **B. Jamuna Madam** Asst. Professor in E.C.E. Department for her excellent guidance right from the selection of Project and for her encouragement through out the completion of the project.*

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*We are expressing our sincere Thanks to our esteemed principal Sri. **G.V. Satyanarayana Rao** PhD (IIT Madras), permitting this project.*

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Your's sincerely,
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1. ABSTRACT

Most of Artificial Intelligence will eventually lead to robotics. Most neural networking, natural language processing, image recognition, speech recognition/synthesis research aims at eventually incorporating their technology into the epitome of robotics - the creation of a fully humanoid robot.

The field of robotics has been around nearly as long as Artificial Intelligence - but the field has made little progress. This is only natural, since the field not only attempts to conquer intelligence, but also the body that embodies it - a formidable task. Robotics, though, is not just about humanoid robots; but is also about their commercial applications in manufacturing, safety and hundreds of other fields.

It is quite recently that robots have started to employ a degree of Artificial Intelligence in their work - many robots required human operators, or precise guidance throughout their missions. Slowly, robots are becoming more and more autonomous. Robotics is an absolutely fascinating field that interests most people. Robot is a system that contains sensors, control systems, manipulators, power supplies and software-all working together to perform a task. Robot should have Sensing, Movement, Energy and Intelligence characteristics.

This project deals with one of the application of robotics. In this project one moving object is developed which is controlled by Bluetooth technology and able to detect metal automatically. In order to detect the metal, metal detectors were used. Micro controller along with the driver circuit is provided to run the stepper motor. According to the signal from Bluetooth device (connected to a system) robot follows the path, which is driven by a stepper motor. All the obstacles in its path are detected using IR sensors and reported to the host system.

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This project is equipped with Stepper motor, metal detector, IR Sensors, Blue tooth device, and Micro controller along with the Power supply unit. This Robot finds its application in the Defense applications like land mine cleaning, intelligence, security system etc and in the areas like Disaster management.

1.1 INTERFACES USED:

POWER SUPPLY:

The power supply unit is used to provide a constant 5V DC supply to different IC's this is a standard circuits using external 12VDC adapter and fixed 3-pin voltage regulator. Diode is added in series to avoid Reverse voltage.

MICRO CONTROLLER:

The 89C51 is a low cost Micro controller from either ATMEL or PHILIPS. It has a 40-pin configuration and other components are interfaced to its ports. The Micro controller takes input from the external sources and routes them to the appropriate devices as programmed in it. Hence it is the main thing controlling the direction of the robot.

STEPPER MOTOR:

Stepper motors fill a unique niche in the motor control world. These motors are commonly used in measurement and control applications. A 10V, 1.5Amps variable reluctance unipolar stepper motor is used. Here stepper motor converts electronic pulses into Mechanical energy to drive the system.

BLUETOOTH COMMUNICATION:

Bluetooth is the international standard of wireless communication. It uses microwave frequency of about 2.4GHz. Bluetooth technology is optimized for use with WPANs and mobile. Bluetooth technology uses FHSS as a way to deal with undesired interference.

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Bluetooth device can play a role as a master or slave. Master tries to connect itself to other devices and slave is waiting to be connected from other devices. A Bluetooth connection can always be made from pair of master and slave devices. A slave can be in two modes, Inquiry scan or Page scan mode. Inquiry scan mode is waiting for a packet of Inquiry from other Bluetooth device and Page scan mode is waiting for the packet of connection from other Bluetooth device. Every Bluetooth device has its unique address, called BD (Bluetooth Device) address, which is composed of twelve hexadecimal digits which is used frequently while establishing the link among the Bluetooth devices.

METAL DETECTOR:

Metal detector detects the metals present under the ground. It sends the information to the master device (system) through blue tooth technology.

IR SENSOR:

The IR Sensors traces out any obstacles in its path. The signal strength of the IR Sensors gives the presence of any obstacle to the robot.

1.2 BLOCK DIAGRAM:

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ROBOT CONTROL USING BLUETOOTH TECHNOLOGY

2. BLUETOOTH PROFILE

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Bluetooth is low cost, low power short-range radio technology originally developed as a cable replacement to connect devices such as mobile phone handsets, headsets and portable computers. No longer do people need to connect, plug into, install, enable or configure anything to anything else.

The Bluetooth specification is an open, global specification defining the complete system from the radio right up to the application level. Version 1.0 of the Bluetooth came into existence in 1994 when Ericsson Mobile Communication began its study for alternatives to replace the cable and this technology hit the market in 1999. This study concluded with radio link as a better option than the optical communication like infrared because of its line of sight limitation.

It is not possible to get universal acceptance for a new technology developed by a single company particularly for blue tooth, because numerous corporations are designing and producing vast range of telecom gadgets.

Then they formed Bluetooth Special Interest Group (SIG) to define and promote Bluetooth specification with five key promoters:

- ❖ Ericsson Mobile Communications
- ❖ Intel Corp.
- ❖ IBM Corp.
- ❖ Toshiba Corp.
- ❖ Nokia Mobile Phones

Bluetooth devices operate at 2.4 GHz globally available license free band. This band is reserved for general purpose usage of Industrial, Scientific and Medical applications. Thus Bluetooth has to be very robust because many users, polluters of this shared spectrum.

The operating band is divided into 1MHz spaced channels signaling data at 1 mega signals per second for the sake of obtaining maximum available bandwidth. Its modulation

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scheme is Frequency Shift Keying (FSK). Technical robustness is not possible if the Bluetooth devices operate on the constant frequency. Bluetooth devices have to jump to another frequency continuously within the available bandwidth. After sending a packet both devices has to jump another radio channel effectively, this is called Frequency Hopping Spread Spectrum (FHSS). Each Bluetooth timeslot lasts for 625 micro seconds. Generally Bluetooth devices hop for every packet or every 2 packet or every 5 packets.

Bluetooth is mainly designed for low power radio frequency link available in the range of 10m, 20m and 100m. Bluetooth specification allows three different powers they are referred as three classes of Bluetooth devices.

Bluetooth devices can operate in two modes for data transfer using Bluetooth devices one has to act as Master and other as Slave. It is the Master which initiates the transaction, establishes the link with slave. Most importantly Master decides the Frequency Hoping Spectrum, which Slave has to follow. One Master can have maximum seven slaves thus it has to decide seven different Frequency Hoping Spectrums.

Every Bluetooth device has a unique Bluetooth device address, and a Bluetooth clock. The base band part of the Bluetooth specification describes an algorithm, which can calculate frequency hop sequence from a Bluetooth device address and a Bluetooth clock. When Slaves connect to a Master, they are told the Bluetooth device address and clock of the Master. They then use this to calculate the frequency hop sequence. Because all Slaves use the Master's clock and address, all are synchronized to the Master's frequency hop sequence.

The Master controls the frequency hop sequence, when devices are allowed to transmit. The Master controls how the total available bandwidth is divided among the Slaves by deciding when and how often to communicate with each Slave. The number of time slots among multiple devices is called Time Division Multiplexing.

2.1 PICO NETS AND SCATTER NETS:

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A collection of Slave device operating together with one common Master is referred as a Pico net. Pico net follow the frequency hopping sequence and timing of the Master.

Fig:1 Point to Point and Point to Multipoint Piconets

In fig.1, the Pico net on the left with only one Slave illustrates a point-to-point connection. The Pico net on the right with three Slaves talking to the Master illustrates a point to multipoint connection. The Slaves in a Pico net only have links to the Master and there are no direct links between Slaves in a Pico net.

The number of Slaves in a Pico net is seven, with each Slave only communicating with the shared Master.

When a device is present in more than one Pico net is called Scatter net. It must be time-shared, spending a few slots on one Pico net and a few slots on the other. On the left side of the scatter net, where one device is a Slave in one Pico net and a Master in another.

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On the right side scatter net where one device is a Slave in two Pico nets. It is not possible to have a device which is Master of two different Pico nets since all Slaves in a Pico net are synchronized to the Masters Hop sequence. By definition, all devices with the same Master must be on the same Pico net.

Fig2: Scatternets

2.2 RADIO POWER CLASSES:

Bluetooth specification allows three different powers they are referred as three classes of Bluetooth devices.

- Class 1 = 100mW(for 100m radius)
- Class 2 = 2.5mW(for 20m radius)
- Class 3 = 1mW(for 10m radius)

The maximum range for a Class 1, 100mW radio is about 100meters. There is also a minimum range for a Bluetooth connection. If radios are put too close together, the receiver saturates; so, the minimum range for a Bluetooth radio link is around 10cm.

2.3 RADIO INTERFACE:

2.3.1 FREQUENCY HOPPING:

Frequency hopping is really is at the heart of Bluetooth. It is a secure and robust communication. Both attributes of the techniques are important for the Bluetooth. Although Bluetooth provides a re-transmission for lost data packets, it is altogether more efficient and robust to retransmit the data on a new channel, which is unlikely to also be blocked. Indeed, the algorithm employed to calculate the hop sequence ensures maximum distance between adjacent hop channels in the sequence. Also several active Bluetooth Pico nets may be within range of each other; with each Pico net hopping independently with a pseudo random sequence based on each Pico net's identity/access code, collisions will be minimized. This is important as all Bluetooth device only has x79 channels in which to operate. In office or public environment, the number of active devices can very quickly reach this limit, and a low correlation between non-communicating pairs.

2.3.2 MODULATION:

The operating band of 83.5MHz is divided into 1MHz spaced channels, each signaling data at 1M Symbols per second so as to obtain the maximum available

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channel bandwidth. With the chosen modulation scheme of GFSK (Gaussian Frequency Shift Keying), this equates to 1Mb/s. A binary 1 gives rise to a positive frequency deviation from the nominal carrier frequency, while a binary 0 gives rise to a negative frequency deviation.

To obtain the most efficient use of bandwidth while still maintaining acceptable error probability, the digital bit stream is modulated using GFSK with a BT product of 0.5 and a modulation index of between 0.28 and 0.35. The BT product is the product of adjacent signal frequency separation (0.5MHz) and symbol duration (1us). A BT product of 0.5 corresponds to the minimum carrier separation to ensure orthogonally (i.e., no cross correlation) between signals in adjacent channels. The modulation index represents the strength of the peak frequency deviation (f_d) and can be expressed as $2f_dT$, where T is the symbol duration. This translates to a frequency deviation range of 140 KHz to 175 KHz. The Bluetooth specification gives 115 KHz as an absolute minimum deviation.

GFSK employs a Gaussian filter to smooth the frequency transitions so that the modulated carrier frequency changes smoothly with a Gaussian shaped envelope. This maintains continuous phase of the carrier frequency and reduces the emitted spectral side lobes, allowing better spectral efficiency and less inter-symbol interference. The Gaussian filter acts on the transmit bit stream and may be implemented in the radio as an analog filter, carried out in the digital part of the base band using a FIR filter implemented as a Linear Feedback Shift Register(LFSR), or as part of a modulation lookup table.

2.3.3 POWER EMISSION AND CONTROL:

FCC regulations permit transmit power up to 0dBm in the ISM band without spread spectrum operation. For high power emissions, a spread spectrum scheme must be adopted through the use of frequency hopping, Bluetooth is able to operate at up to 20dBm, allowing a range of up to 100m.

Here power classes are defined in the Bluetooth specification (see table.1). Power Class3 is the most common scheme adopted by manufacturers, and of course is the lowest power consumption option. Power Class 1 has a mandatory requirement for power control, while classes 2 or 3 make this optional. Although for minimum power consumption, power control is always preferable.

Power Class	Output Power (Max)	Minimum Output	Power Control at Max Setting

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1	100mW (20dBm)	1mw (0dBm)	Mandatory: +4dBm to 20dBm Optional:-30dbm to 4dBm
2	2.5mW (4dBm)	0.25mW (-6dBm)	Optional:-30dBm to 4dBm
3	1mw (0dBm)	-	Optional:-30dBm to 4dBm

Table1: Transmit Power Classes

Power control operates by a receiver monitoring the Received Signal Strength Indication and sending LMP control commands back to the transmitter, asking for their transmit power to be reduced if the RSSI value is higher than that strictly necessary to maintain a satisfactory link. Should RSSI value drop too low, then the receiver may request the power to be increased. The specification requires power to be controlled in steps of 2dB to 8dB, while RSSI measurements must be accurate to ± 4 dB at -60 dBm, with a minimum range of operation of 20 ± 6 dB, starting at -60 dB.

2.3.4 APPLICATIONS:

The kind of range one can get using Bluetooth again depends on the number of physical objects available in the surrounding area which always absorb the microwave frequency there by reducing the distance of propagation. Bluetooth enables us to work with verity of telephone devices such as

- Mobile cellular phone to Public Switched Telephone Network (PSTN) through access point
- Mobile cellular phone to notebook PC

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- Mobile cellular phone to headset
- Communication between laptop to palm top.

The Bluetooth implemented in this application is belonging to Class 1 giving 100 meters radius. But in real time applications we need to adopt satellite communication to have link with Bluetooth which will be again in microwave band.

2.4 ANTENNAS:

2.4.1 RADIATION PATTERN:

Antenna radiation patterns are usually plotted in two dimensions, they are azimuth and elevation. The azimuth pattern is the pattern of radiation looking down on the antenna from above and the elevation pattern of radiation looking at the antenna from the side.

A dipole antenna radiates in a torrid pattern (a doughnut shape). The Fig.3 shows the radiation patterns. At the left is the azimuth pattern, the radiation is a perfect circle with the same strength in all directions. At the right is the elevation pattern, the sides of the antenna, the radiation is strong dropping away to nothing above and below the antenna.

Azimuth Pattern (Top view)

Elevation Pattern (Side view)

Fig .3 Azimuth and elevation patterns for a dipole antenna

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The radiation pattern of an antenna is useful in designing Bluetooth products because it tells you what the signal strength will look like from different angles to the product.

For example of a dipole aerial given above, the antenna works best if it is at 90° to the path leading to the device it is communicating with. So if devices are spaced out horizontally, dipoles work best if they are kept vertical. On the other hand there is still good signal strength at up to a 45° angle, so the product could be held at a angle and the aerial would still work, or products could be spaced out with say a laptop on a desk and a cellular phone under the desk, and there would still be a good chance of the two devices getting a good enough signal to connect.

2.4.2 TYPES OF ANTENNAS:

The most popular antenna types for Bluetooth devices are dipole, flat panel, and micro strip.

DIPOLE ANTENNA:

Dipole antennas are cylinders, with the signal usually feeding in from the bottom. Very simple dipole antennas are often made out of short sections of coaxial cable for development purpose.

As the elevation pattern show in fig.3, a dipole antenna transmits best from the side of the antenna. Usually it is fed from the base of the antenna, but it can also be fed from the center of one side.

(1) Dipole Antenna

Fig: Dipole Antenna

The length of a dipole antenna must be related to the wavelength of the signal it is carrying. Half wave and a quarter wave dipoles are commonly used.

FLAT PANEL ANTENNA:

Flat Panel antennas are small metal patches, and are usually square or rectangular. They are strongly directional, and so their radiation pattern is not ideal for handheld devices. On the other hand, they can be made very small for the ISM band, and can be mounted directly onto PCBs, both of which help to reduce costs.

A popular form of flat panel antenna used in Bluetooth devices is a Planar Inverted F Antenna. This antenna is named for its resemblance to a capital F on its side. It has a flat panel as far away from the ground as possible, and is fed by two contacts, which form the arms of the F.

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MICRO STRIP:

Micro strip antennas are simply patterns on PCBs.

The radio module of the Ericsson Bluetooth Developer's Kit comes with a micro strip antenna, which is implemented as a printed pattern on a small PCB.

2.5 BLUETOOTH MODULE:

Parani-ESD is a module device for wireless serial communication using Bluetooth technology that is international standard for short range wireless communications. Parani-ESD can communicate with other Bluetooth devices that support the Serial Port Profile.

Parani-ESD lineup has several models with different communication ranges from 30m (Parani-ESD200/210) up to 100m (Parani-ESD100/110) for use with various applications. The Parani-ESD delivers better quality of communication than a standard RS232 cables.

Parani-ESD has a compact design and can be placed conveniently into devices or equipment. Its detachable antenna optimizes the quality and distance for wireless communications. Parani-ESD supports FHSS (Frequency Hopping Spread Spectrum), which is a technique, native to Bluetooth that allows the Parani-ESD minimize radio interference while decreasing the likelihood of over-air hijacking. Parani-ESD also supports authentication and Bluetooth data encryption.

Parani-ESD can be configured and controlled by typical AT commands. Users can easily configure Parani-ESD by using a terminal program such as HyperTerminal and can use Bluetooth wireless communication without modifying user's existing serial communication program. In addition to the basic AT commands, Parani-ESD provides some expanded AT commands for various functions. User friendly Parani Wizard and Parani WIN are also provided for easy setup on Microsoft Windows.

2.5.1 PANEL LAYOUT:

Fig: *The Panel Layout of Jig Board.*

2.6 CONNECTING THE HARDWARE:

This section describes how to connect the Parani-ESD Series to the Jig Board and the Jig Board to the serial device for initial testing.

- Connect the Parani-ESD Series to the Jig Board.
- Connect a power source to Jig Board for the Parani-ESD Series.
- Connect Jig Board for the Parani-ESD Series to a serial device.

CONNECTING PARANI-ESD TO JIG BOARD:

- Connect the Parani-ESD Series to the Jig Board as shown below.

Fig: connecting Parani-ESD to Jig Board

CONNECTING POWER TO JIG BOARD:

Connect the power jack to the power connector of the Jig Board for the Parani-ESD Series using the DC power adapter or USB power cable that is included in the package.

Fig: Connecting Power to Jig Board

CONNECTING A DEVICE TO JIG BOARD:

Connect the serial data cable between the Jig Board and the serial device. If necessary, supply power to the serial device attached to the Jig Board.

Fig: Connecting a Device to Jig Board

2.7 CONFIGURATION:

OPERATION MODES:

The Parani-ESD requires also includes some settings for Bluetooth. For getting the most out of Parani-ESD, user should understand the following Bluetooth connection schemes.

A Bluetooth device can play a role as a master or slave. Master tries to connect itself to other Bluetooth devices, and slave is waiting to be connected from other Bluetooth devices. A Bluetooth connection is always made by a pair of master and slave devices. A slave can be in two modes, Inquiry Scan or Page Scan mode. Inquiry Scan mode is waiting for a packet of inquiry from other Bluetooth device and Page Scan mode is waiting for a packet of connection from other Bluetooth device. Every Bluetooth device has its unique address, called BD (Bluetooth Device) address, which is composed of 12 hexadecimal numbers.

PARANI-ESD HAS 4 OPERATION MODES AS FOLLOWS:

MODE DESCRIPTION:

2.7.1 Mode0:

In this mode, there is no response when power on or software reset, and Parani-ESD is just waiting for AT command input. Neither master nor slave is assigned to Parani-ESD in mode0. User can change the configuration parameters of Parani-ESD in this mode. Parani-ESD must be in Mode0, when it is directly controlled by AT commands. The factory default is set to Mode0.

2.7.2 Mode1:

Parani-ESD tries to connect the last connected Bluetooth device. Parani-ESD in Mode1 is to be a master and tries to connect the last connected Bluetooth device. Parani-ESD always stores the BD address of the Bluetooth device to which Parani-ESD has connected last. When Parani-ESD is initially used or after hardware reset, there is no BD address stored in Parani-ESD. In this case, Mode1 will not be able to work properly. The mode change to Mode1 can be made after Parani-ESD succeeds to connect to one other Bluetooth device. Once changed to Mode1, Parani-ESD will try to connect automatically the last connected Bluetooth device whenever the unit is powered on or software reset. Parani-ESD in Mode1 cannot be discovered or connected by other Bluetooth devices.

2.7.3 Mode2:

Parani-ESD is waits for a connection from the last connected Bluetooth device. Parani-ESD in Mode2 is to be a slave and waiting for the connection only from the last connected Bluetooth device. Just like Mode1, if there is no BD address stored in Parani-ESD, the mode change from other operation modes to Mode2 is not work properly. Once changed to Mode2, Parani-ESD will wait for the connection from the last connected Bluetooth device whenever the unit is powered on or software reset. Parani-ESD in Mode2

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cannot be discovered or connected to Bluetooth devices other than the last connected device.

2.7.4 Mode3:

Parani-ESD is waiting for the connection from any other Bluetooth devices. In Mode 3 the Parani -ESD is discoverable and can be connected to by other Bluetooth devices.

SERIAL PORTS:

The applicable settings for serial ports are as follows.

Serial Port Settings	Values
Baud rate	1200, 2400, 4800, 9600 , 19200, 38200, 57600, 115200, 230400
Data bite	8
Parity	No parity Even parity, Odd parity
Stop bit	1 2
Hardware Flow Control	Use, No Use

2.8 HARDWARE FLOW CONTROL:

Parani-ESD plugged into its host system transmits data from host to the other side Bluetooth device. This data is saved temporarily in the internal buffer of Parani-ESD and sent repeatedly until the transmission is completed packet by packet. When the radio transmission condition is not good enough to send data promptly, it can cause a transmission delay. If the host sends more data when the buffer is full, buffer overflow will make Parani-ESD malfunction consequently. In order to prevent this buffer overflow, Parani-ESD works as follows.

When using hardware flow control, Parani-ESD disables RTS so that it stops receiving any further data from the host when the buffer becomes full. RTS will be re-enabled again to begin receiving data from the host when the buffer has created more room for more data. When hardware flow control is not being used, the Parani-ESD clears the

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buffer to secure room for the next data when the buffer becomes full. This can mean a loss of data may occur. As the transmission data becomes large, the possibility of data loss becomes greater. For large data transmissions, the use of hardware flow control is highly recommended.

2.8.1 PIN ASSIGNMENT:

Fig: Assignment of Parani-ESD100/110

Pin #	Signal	Direction	Description	Signal Level
1	GND	-	Power Ground	Ground
2	TxD	Output	UART Data Output	TTL
3	RxD	Input	UART Data Input	TTL
4	RTS	Output	UART Ready to Send	TTL
5	CTS	Input	UART Clear to Send	TTL
6	VDD	Input	DC Input (3.0~3.3V)	Power
7	Pairing	Input	Pairing Input (Active Low)	TTL
8	Status	Output	Bluetooth Connect Detect (Active Low)	TTL
9	DSR	Input	Data Set Ready	TTL
10	DTR	Output	Data Terminal Ready	TTL
11	RST	Input	Reset (Active Low)	TTL
12	GND	-	Power Ground	Ground

2.8.2 PARANI-ESD200/210:

Fig: Assignment of Parani-ESD200/210

Pin #	Signal	Direction	Description	Signal Level
1	GND	-	Power Ground	Ground
2	VDD	Input	DC Input (3.0~3.3V)	Power
3	Status	Output	Bluetooth Connect Detect (Active Low)	TTL
4	RST	Input	Reset (Active Low)	TTL
5	CTS	Input	UART Clear to Send	TTL
6	RTS	Output	UART Ready to Send	TTL
2	TxD	Output	UART Data Output	TTL
3	RxD	Input	UART Data Input	TTL

2.8.3 DCD SIGNAL:

Status of Bluetooth connection will be delivered to Host PC via DCD line. When Bluetooth connection is made, DCD signal will be in the OFF state. When disconnecting a Bluetooth connection, DCD signal will be in the ON state.

Connection Module → Low signal

2.8.4 RST SIGNAL:

RST signal will be used for setting the Parani-ESD to factory defaults. RST should be on 0V status

2.8.5 HARDWARE DESIGN:

Fig: When TTL level of MICOM is 5V.

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2.9 COMMANDS:

AT+ :

SD Response: OK.

Purpose: Check the connection status with host equipment.

Description:

Check if the connection to host equipment is operating normally. The serial parameters of Parani-ESD must be same as those of host equipment. If not, the ESD will not respond or 'ERROR' message will appear or an abnormal sequence of strings will appear.

AT+BTINFO? ↓:

SD Response: 112233445566, Device Name, Mode, Status, Auth, Encrypt, Flow Control
OK

Purpose: Display Bluetooth settings

Description:

The current Bluetooth settings are displayed including BD address, Device name, Operation mode, Operation status, Authentication, Data Encryption, and Hardware Flow Control.

Mode	=	MODE0/MODE1/MODE2/MODE3
Status	=	STANDBY/PENDING/CONNECT
Auth	=	0/1 (Authentication is not activated when 0)
Encrypt	=	0/1 (Encryption is not activated when 0)
Flow Control	=	HWFC/NoFC

AT+BTSCAN↓:

SD Response: OK

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Purpose: Wait for inquiry and connection from other Bluetooth devices

Description:

This allows the inquiry and connection from the other Bluetooth devices. The operation status will be in 'Pending' after this command. When connection is made and released, the operation status is back to 'Pending'. To convert the operation status to 'Standby' AT+BTCANCEL must be used. This has the same effect as AT+BTSCAN,3,0. When connection is made with other Bluetooth device, SD response will be 'CONNECT' with its BD address.

BTMODE3↓:

SD Response: OK.

Purpose: Set operation mode

Parameters n=0: MODE0 (Default)

n=1: MODE1

n=2: MODE2

n=3: MODE3

Description:

When the operation status is 'Pending' currently, change the status to 'Standby' with AT+BTCANCEL prior to this command. To take effect the ATZ must be executed or Power cycle the unit.

AT+BTINQ?↓:

SD Response: OK.

Purpose: Search Bluetooth devices nearby

Description:

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The Bluetooth devices in Inquiry scan mode nearby are displayed with their BD addresses, Device names, and Class of device. Maximum 10 devices are scanned for 30 seconds.

ATD <bt address>↵ :

SD Response: OK/ ERROR.

Purpose: Connect to the last connected Bluetooth device

Description:

Parani-ESD saves the BD address of the Bluetooth device most recently connected to. If it fails to make a connection, SD response will display an 'ERROR'.

+++ ↵:

SD Response: OK.

Purpose: Convert the operation status of 'Connect' to 'Standby'

Description:

In 'Connect' status, data from host is transmitted to the other side Bluetooth device, and any AT command is not accepted but this command, which is not echoed on the screen. When Parani-ESD encounters a character '+' from host, it stops the data transmission and waits for next 2 characters. If the next 2 characters aren't both '+', it restart to transmit data including the first '+' as well. If not, it converts the operation status to 'Standby'. If the data from host includes '+++', it will convert the operation status to 'Standby'.

Notice that Parani-ESD holds data transmission when it encounters '+', until receiving next character. '+' is an escape sequence character by default, which is changeable by AT+SETESC.

ATH ↵ :

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SD Response: OK / DISCONNECT.

Purpose: Release the current connection

Description:

The current Bluetooth connection will be disconnected. It takes about 30 seconds to detect an abnormal disconnection such as power off and moving out of service range.

AT&F␣:

SD Response : OK.

Purpose: Hardware reset

Description:

This has the same effect as initialization by pressing the factory reset button. All parameters are initialized to factory defaults.

3. P89C51 MICROCONTROLLER

3.1 INTRODUCTION OF MICROCONTROLLER:

BASIC MICROCONTROLLER BLOCK DIAGRAM:

There are three busses involved in accessing memory:

Address bus

Data bus

Control bus

3.1.1 READ CYCLE:

1. CPU places address on address bus.
2. Control signals memory - address on address bus is valid
3. Memory chip fetches data from location specified by the address and places on the data bus
4. Control signals CPU - data on data bus is valid

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5. CPU takes data from data bus

3.1.2 WRITE CYCLE:

1. CPU places address on address bus
2. Control signals memory - address on address bus is valid.
3. CPU places data on the data bus
4. Control signals memory - data on data bus is valid
5. Memory chip takes data from data bus and places it in the Location specified by the address

3.2 BASIC DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MICROPROCESSOR AND MICROCONTROLLER:

A microprocessor system consists of a microprocessor with memory, input ports and output ports connected to it externally. A microcontroller is a single chip containing a microprocessor, memory, input ports and output ports. Since all four blocks reside on the one chip, a microcontroller is much faster than a microprocessor system

3.2.1 MEMORY:

We can split memory into two types;

RAM and ROM

RAM stands for random access memory. There are two features of RAM which distinguish it from ROM

RAM is read/write - data can be written to and read from RAM

RAM is volatile - data is lost once the power to a RAM chip is lost

Random access refers to the fact that data from any location in the memory chip is accessible at any time (you simply put the desired address on the address bus).

ROM stands for read only memory. As with RAM, it is random access but it differs from RAM in two ways:

ROM, as the name suggests, is read only. You cannot write to a ROM chip. A ROM chip must be programmed, but once programmed, it cannot be (easily) changed ROM is non-volatile - when power is removed from the chip data is not lost.

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There are many types of ROM available; PROM, EPROM, EEPROM and Flash are the most common.

3.3 MICRO CONTROLLER 89C51:

The 8051 is just one of the MCS-51 families of microcontrollers developed by Intel. The design of each of the MCS-51 microcontrollers is more or less the same. The differences between each member of the family are the amount of on-chip memory and the number of timers.

Phillips 89C51 contains a non-volatile FLASH program memory that is parallel programmable. Phillips 89C51, 8-bit Micro controller from MCS-51 Intel family, with 4K bytes of flash and 128 bytes of internal RAM had been used. It has a 40-pin configuration and other components interfaced to its ports. The Micro controller takes input from the external sources and routes them to the appropriate devices as programmed in it.

3.3.1 FEATURES:

- 89C51 Central Processing Unit
- On-chip FLASH Program Memory
- Speedup to 33 MHz
- Fully Static Operation
- RAM expandable externally up to 64 Kbytes
- Four interrupt priority levels
- Six interrupt sources
- Four 8-bit input output ports
- Full-duplex enhanced UART
- Framing error detection
- Automatic address recognition
- Three 16-bit timers/counters T0, T1 and additional T2
- Programmable clock out
- Second DPTR register

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- Asynchronous port reset

Power control modes

- Clock can be stopped and resumed
- Idle mode
- Power down mode
- Low EMI
- Wakeup from power down by an external interrupt
- Non-volatile FLASH program memory that is parallel programmable
- Flash memory features
- FLASH EPROM internal program memory with chip erases.
- Up to 64K byte external program memory if the internal program memory is disabled
- Programmable security bits.
- 10,000 minimum erase/program cycles for each byte

3.3.2 8051 MICRO CONTROLLER ARCHITECTURE:

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BLOCK DIAGRAM

3.4 DESCRIPTION OF BLOCK DIAGRAM:

3.4.1 CPU:

BLOCK DIAGRAM OF CPU:

The microcontroller consists of eight bit Arithmetic Logic Unit (ALU), Associated Register Array means registers like register A, register B, PSW (program status word), SP (stack pointer), and a 16-bit PC (program counter) and a 16-bit DPTR (data pointer) register

3.4.2 ALU:

The ALU performs arithmetic and logic functions on 8-bit variables. The ALU can perform addition, subtraction, multiplication and division and the logic unit can perform logical operations. An important and unique feature of the microcontroller architecture is that the ALU can also manipulate 1 bit as well as 8-bit data types. Individual bits may be set, cleared, complemented, moved, tested and used in logic computation.

3.4.3 ACCUMULATOR:

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The Accumulator, as its name suggests, is used as a general register to accumulate the results of a large number of instructions. It can hold an 8-bit (1-byte) value and is the most versatile register, the microcontroller has due to the sheer number of instructions that make use of the accumulator. Accumulator holds a source of operand and stores the result of the arithmetic operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication and division. The accumulator can be the source or destination register for logical operations. The accumulator has several exclusive functions such as rotate, parity computation; testing for 0, sign acceptor etc. and so on.

3.4.4 PROGRAM COUNTER:

The program counter points to the address of the next instruction to be executed. As the CPU fetches the opcode from the program ROM, the program counter is implemented to point to the next instruction. The Microcontroller can access program addresses 0000 to FFFFH, a total of 64K bytes of code.

When the 8051 is initialized PC always starts at 0000h and is incremented each time an instruction is executed. PC is always incremented by one. Since some instructions require 2 or 3 bytes the PC will be incremented by 2 or 3 in these cases. The Program Counter is special in that there is no way to directly modify its value.

3.4.5 TYPES OF MEMORY:

The 8051 has three very general types of memory. To effectively program the 8051 it is necessary to have a basic understanding of these memory types.

The memory types are illustrated in the following diagram. They are:

1. On-Chip Memory
2. External Code Memory

EXTERNAL RAM:

On-Chip Memory refers to any memory (Code, RAM, or other) that physically exists on the microcontroller itself. On-chip memory can be of several types, but we'll get into that shortly.

External Code Memory is code (or program) memory that resides off-chip. This is often in the form of an external EPROM.

External RAM is RAM memory that resides off-chip. This is often in the form of standard static RAM or flash RAM.

CODE MEMORY:

Code memory is the memory that holds the actual 8051 program that is to be run. This memory is limited to 64K and comes in many shapes and sizes. Code memory may be found *on-chip*, either burned into the microcontroller as ROM or EPROM. Code may also be stored completely *off-chip* in an external ROM or, more commonly, an external EPROM. Flash RAM is also another popular method of storing a program. Various combinations of these memory types may also be used--that is to say, it is possible to have 4K of code memory *on-chip* and 64k of code memory *off-chip* in an EPROM.

When the program is stored on-chip the 64K maximum is often reduced to 4k, 8k, or 16k. This varies depending on the version of the chip that is being used. Each version offers specific capabilities and one of the distinguishing factors from chip to chip is how much ROM/EPROM space the chip has.

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However, code memory is most commonly implemented as off-chip EPROM. This is especially true in low-cost development systems and in systems developed by students.

EXTERNAL RAM:

As an obvious opposite of *Internal RAM*, the 8051 also supports what is called *External RAM*.

External RAM is any random access memory which is found *off-chip*. Since the memory is off-chip it is not as flexible in terms of accessing, and is also slower. For example, to increment an Internal RAM location by 1 requires only 1 instruction and 1 instruction cycle. To increment a 1-byte value stored in External RAM requires 4 instructions and 7 instruction cycles. In this case, external memory is 7 times slower!

What if External RAM loses in speed and flexibility it gains in quantity? While Internal RAM is limited to 128 bytes (256 bytes with an 8052) and 8051 supports External RAM up to 64K.

ON-CHIP MEMORY:

The 8051 includes a certain amount of on-chip memory. On-chip memory is really one of two types: Internal RAM and Special Function Register (SFR) memory. The layout of the 8051's internal memory is presented in the following memory map:

IRAM Addr									Description									
00	R0	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	Reg. Bank 0									
08	R0	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	Reg. Bank 1									
10	R0	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	Reg. Bank 2									
18	R0	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	Reg. Bank 3									
20	00	08	10	18	20	28	30	38	Bits 00-3F									
28	40	48	50	58	60	68	70	78	Bits 40-7F									
30	<div style="background-color: yellow; border: 2px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;"> General User RAM & Stack Space (80 bytes, 30h-7Fh) </div>								General IRAM									
7F																		
80										<div style="background-color: cyan; border: 2px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;"> Special Function Registers (SFRs) (80h - FFh) </div>								SFRs
:																		
:																		

As is illustrated in this map, the 8051 has a bank of 128 bytes of *Internal RAM*. This Internal RAM is found *on-chip* on the 8051 so it is the fastest RAM available, and it is also the most flexible in terms of reading, writing, and modifying its contents. Internal RAM is volatile, so when the 8051 is reset this memory is cleared.

The 128 bytes of internal ram is subdivided as shown on the memory map. The first 8 bytes (00h - 07h) are "register bank 0". By manipulating certain SFRs, a program may choose to use register banks 1, 2, or 3. These alternative register banks are located in internal RAM in addresses 08h through 1Fh. We'll discuss "register banks" more in a later chapter. For now it is sufficient to know that they "live" and are part of internal RAM.

Bit Memory also lives and is part of internal RAM. We'll talk more about bit memory very shortly, but for now just keep in mind that bit memory actually resides in internal RAM, from addresses 20h through 2Fh.

The 80 bytes remaining of Internal RAM, from addresses 30h through 7Fh, may be used by user variables that need to be accessed frequently or at high-speed. This area is also utilized by the microcontroller as a storage area for the operating *stack*. This fact severely limits the 8051s stack since, as illustrated in the memory map, the area reserved

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for the stack is only 80 bytes--and usually it is less since 80 bytes has to be shared between the stack and user variables.

3.4.6 REGISTER BANKS:

The 8051 uses 8 "R" registers which are used in many of its instructions. These "R" registers are numbered from 0 through 7 (R0, R1, R2, R3, R4, R5, R6, and R7). These registers are generally used to assist in manipulating values and moving data from one memory location to another however, as the memory map shows; the "R" Register R4 is really part of Internal RAM. The microcontroller has four distinct register banks. When the 8051 is first booted up, register bank 0 (addresses 00h through 07h) is used by default. The register banks really reside in the first 32 bytes of Internal RAM.

3.4.7 BIT MEMORY:

The 8051 being a communications-oriented microcontroller gives the user the ability to access a number of *bit variables*. These variables may be either 1 or 0. There are 128 bit variables available to the user, numbered 00h through 7Fh. The user may make use of these variables with commands such as SETB and CLR. It is important to note that Bit Memory is really a part of Internal RAM. In fact, the 128 bit variables occupy the 16 bytes of Internal RAM from 20h through 2Fh. Bit memory is not really a new type of memory. Its really just a subset of Internal RAM. But since the 8051 provides special instructions to access these 16 bytes of memory on a bit by bit basis it is useful to think of it as a separate type of memory. it is just a subset of Internal RAM--and that operations performed on Internal RAM can change the values of the bit variables.

3.4.8 SPECIAL FUNCTION REGISTER (SFR) MEMORY:

Special Function Registers (SFRs) are areas of memory that control specific functionality of the 8051 processor. For example, four SFRs permit access to the 8051s 32 input/output lines. Another SFR allows a program to read or write to the 8051s serial port. Other SFRs allow the user to set the serial baud rate, control and access timers, and configure the 8051s interrupt system. Program may inspect and/or change the operating mode of the 8051 by manipulating the values of the 8051's Special Function Registers. The SFR is part of Internal Memory.

The program may inspect and/or change the operating mode of the 8051 by manipulating the values of the 8051's Special Function Registers. SFRs are accessed as if they were normal Internal RAM. The only difference is that Internal RAM is from address 00h through 7Fh whereas SFR registers exist in the address range of 80h through FFh Each SFR has an address (80h through FFh) and a name.

THE DIAGRAM OF THE SFR:

80	P0	SP	DPL	DPH				PCON	87
88	TCON	TMOD	TL0	TL1	TH0	TH1			8F
90	P1								97
98	SCON	SBUF							9F
A0	P2								A7
A8	IE								AF
B0	P3								B7
B8	IP								B9
C0									C7
C8									CF
D0	PSW								D7
D8									DF
E0	ACC								E7
E8									EF
F0	B								F7
F8									FF

Blue background are I/O port SFRs
 Yellow background are control SFRs
 Green background are other SFRs

Although the address range of 80h through FFh offers 128 possible addresses, there are only 21 SFRs in a standard 8051. All other addresses in the SFR range (80h through FFh) are considered invalid. Writing to or reading from these registers may produce undefined values or behavior.

3.4.9 SFR TYPES:

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As mentioned in the chart itself, the SFRs that have a blue background are SFRs related to the I/O ports. The 8051 has four I/O ports of 8 bits, for a total of 32 I/O lines. Whether a given I/O line is high or low and the value read from the line are controlled by the SFRs in green.

The SFRs with yellow background are SFRs which in some way control the operation or the configuration of some aspect of the 8051. For example, TCON controls the timers, SCON controls the serial port.

The remaining SFRs, with green backgrounds, are "other SFRs." These SFRs can be thought of as auxiliary SFRs in the sense that they don't directly configure the 8051 but obviously the 8051 cannot operate without them. For example, once the serial port has been configured using SCON, the program may read or write to the serial port using the SBUF register.

3.4.10 SFR DESCRIPTIONS:

P0 (Port 0, Address 80h, Bit-Addressable): This is input/output port 0. Each bit of this SFR corresponds to one of the pins on the microcontroller. For example, bit 0 of port 0 is pin P0.0, bit 7 is pin P0.7. Writing a value of 1 to a bit of this SFR will send a high level on the corresponding I/O pin whereas a value of 0 will bring it to a low level.

SP (Stack Pointer, Address 81h): This is the stack pointer of the microcontroller. This SFR indicates where the next value to be taken from the stack will be read from in Internal RAM. If you push a value onto the stack, the value will be written to the address of SP + 1. That is to say, if SP holds the value 07h, a PUSH instruction will push the value onto the stack at address 08h. This SFR is modified by all instructions which modify the stack, such as PUSH, POP, CALL, RET, RETI, and whenever interrupts are provoked by the microcontroller.

3.4.11 DPL/DPH (Data Pointer Low/High, Addresses 82h/83h):

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The SFRs DPL and DPH work together to represent a 16-bit value called the *Data Pointer*. The data pointer is used in operations regarding external RAM and some instructions involving code memory. Since it is an unsigned two-byte integer value, it can represent values from 0000h to FFFFh (0 through 65,535 decimal).

PCON (Power Control, Addresses 87h): The Power Control SFR is used to control the 8051's power control modes. Certain operation modes of the 8051 allow the 8051 to go into a type of "sleep" mode which requires much less power. These modes of operation are controlled through PCON. Additionally, one of the bits in PCON is used to double the effective baud rate of the 8051's serial port.

3.4.12 TCON (Timer Control, Addresses 88h, Bit-Addressable):

The Timer Control SFR is used to configure and modify the way in which the 8051's two timers operate. This SFR controls whether each of the two timers is running or stopped and contains a flag to indicate that each timer has overflowed. Additionally, some non-timer related bits are located in the TCON SFR. These bits are used to configure the way in which the external interrupts are activated and also contain the external interrupt flags which are set when an external interrupt has occurred.

3.4.13 TMOD (Timer Mode, Addresses 89h):

The Timer Mode SFR is used to configure the mode of operation of each of the two timers. Using this SFR your program may configure each timer to be a 16-bit timer, an 8-bit auto reload timer, a 13-bit timer, or two separate timers. Additionally, you may configure the timers to only count when an external pin is activated or to count "events" that are indicated on an external pin.

TIMER 0 AND TIMER 1:

The "timer" or "counter" function is selected by control bits C/T in the special function register TMOD. These two timer/counters have for operating modes, which are selected by bit-pairs (M1/M0) in TMOD. Modes 0, 1, and 2 are the same for both timers/counters. Mode 3 is different.

TL0/TH0 (Timer 0 Low/High, Addresses 8Ah/8Ch):

These two SFRs, taken together, represent timer 0. Their exact behavior depends on how the timer is configured in the TMOD SFR; however, these timers always count up. What is configurable is how and when they increment in value.

GATE: When set, start and stop of timer by hardware
 When reset, start and stop of timer by software

C/T: Cleared for timer operation
 Set for counter operation

M1	M0	MODE	OPERATING MODE
0	0	0	13-bit timer mode
0	1	1	16-bit timer mode
1	0	2	8-bit auto reload mode
1	1	3	Split timer mode

TL1/TH1 (Timer 1 Low/High, Addresses 8Bh/8Dh):

These two SFRs, taken together, represent timer 1. Their exact behavior depends on how the timer is configured in the TMOD SFR; however, these timers always count up. What is configurable is how and when they increment in value.

Address =88H.

Bit addressable

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TF: Timer overflow flag: Set by hardware when the timer/counter overflows. It is cleared by hardware, as the processor vectors to the interrupt service routine.

TR: timer run control bit: Set or cleared by software to turn timer or counter on/off.

IE: set by CPU when the external interrupt edge (H-to-L transition) is detected. It is cleared by CPU when the interrupt is processed.

IT: set/cleared by software to specify falling edge/low-level triggered external interrupt.

P1 (Port 1, Address 90h, Bit-Addressable):

This is input/output port 1. Each bit of this SFR corresponds to one of the pins on the microcontroller. For example, bit 0 of port 1 is pin P1.0, bit 7 is pin P1.7. Writing a value of 1 to a bit of this SFR will send a high level on the corresponding I/O pin whereas a value of 0 will bring it to a low level.

3.4.14 SCON (Serial Control, Addresses 98h, Bit-Addressable):

The Serial Control SFR is used to configure the behavior of the 8051's on-board serial port. This SFR controls the baud rate of the serial port, whether the serial port is activated to receive data, and also contains flags that are set when a byte is successfully sent or received.

Bit addressable

REN set or cleared by software to enable or disable reception.

TB 8 not widely used.

RB 8 not widely used.

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TI transmits interrupt flag. Set by hardware at the beginning of the stop bit in mode1. It must be cleared by software.

RI received interrupts flag. Set by hardware halfway through the stop bit time in mode1. It must be cleared by software.

SM0	SM1	Serial mode 0
0	0	Synchronous mode
0	1	8-bit data, 1 start bit, 1 stop bit, variable baud rate
1	0	9- bit data, 1 start bit, 1 stop bit, fixed baud rate
1	1	9- bit data, 1 start bit, 1 stop bit, variable baud rate

3.4.15 SBUF (Serial Control, Addresses 99h):

The Serial Buffer SFR is used to send and receive data via the on-board serial port. Any value written to SBUF will be sent out the serial port's TXD pin. Likewise, any value which the 8051 receives via the serial port's RXD pin will be delivered to the user program via SBUF. In other words, SBUF serves as the output port when written to and as an input port when read from.

3.4.16 P2 (Port 2, Address A0h, Bit-Addressable):

This is input/output port 2. Each bit of this SFR corresponds to one of the pins on the microcontroller. For example, bit 0 of port 2 is pin P2.0, bit 7 is pin P2.7. Writing a value of 1 to a bit of this SFR will send a high level on the corresponding I/O pin whereas a value of 0 will bring it to a low level.

3.4.17 IE (Interrupt Enable, Addresses A8h):

A single microcontroller can serve several devices. In the interrupt method, whenever any device needs its service, the device notifies the microcontroller by sending it an interrupt signal. Upon receiving an interrupt signal, the microcontroller interrupts

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whatever it is doing and serves the device. The program associated with the interrupt is called the interrupt service routine (ISR). The advantageous of interrupts is that the microcontroller can serve many devices based on the priority assigned to it.

3.4.18 SIX INTERRUPTS IN THE 89C51:

1. Reset.
2. Two interrupts are set aside for the timers.
3. Two interrupts are set aside for hardware external hardware interrupts.
4. Serial Communications has a single interrupt (receive and transfer).

The Interrupt Enable SFR is used to enable and disable specific interrupts. The low 7 bits of the SFR are used to enable/disable the specific interrupts, where as the highest bit is used to enable or disable ALL interrupts. Thus, if the high bit of IE is 0 all interrupts are disabled regardless of whether an individual interrupt is enabled by setting a lower bit.

7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
EA	----	ET2	ES	ET1	EX1	ET0	EX0

EA disable all interrupts. If EA = 0, now interrupt is acknowledged. If EA = 1, each interrupt source is individually enabled or disabled by setting or clearing its enable a lap bit.

---- Not implemented, reserved for future use.

ET2 enables or disables timer 2 overflow or capturer interrupt.

ES enables or disables the serial port interrupt.

ET1 enables or disables timer 1 overflow interrupt.

EX1 enables or disables external interrupt 1.

ET0 enables or disables timer 0 overflow interrupt.

EX0 enables or disables external interrupt 0.

P3 (Port 3, Address B0h, Bit-Addressable):

This is input/output port 3. Each bit of this SFR corresponds to one of the pins on the microcontroller. For example, bit 0 of port 3 is pin P3.0, bit 7 is pin P3.7. Writing a

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value of 1 to a bit of this SFR will send a high level on the corresponding I/O pin whereas a value of 0 will bring it to a low level.

IP (Interrupt Priority, Addresses B8h, Bit-Addressable):

The Interrupt Priority SFR is used to specify the relative priority of each interrupt. On the 8051, an interrupt may either be of low (0) priority or high (1) priority. An interrupt may only interrupt interrupts of lower priority. For example, if we configure the 8051 so that all interrupts are of low priority except the serial interrupt, the serial interrupt will always be able to interrupt the system, even if another interrupt is currently executing. However, if a serial interrupt is executing no other interrupt will be able to interrupt the serial interrupt routine since the serial interrupt routine has the highest priority.

--- IP.7 Reserved

--- IP.6 Reserved

PT2 IP.5 Timer2 Interrupt Priority bit (for 8052 only)

PS IP.4 Serial Port Interrupt Priority Bit

PT1 IP.3 Timer1 Interrupt Priority Bit

PX1 IP.2 External Interrupt Priority Bit

PT0 IP.1 Timer0 Interrupt Priority Bit

PX0 IP.0 External Interrupt Priority Bit

3.4.19 PSW (Program Status Word, Addresses D0h, Bit-Addressable):

The Program Status Word is used to store a number of important bits that are set and cleared by microcontroller instructions. The PSW SFR contains the carry flag, the auxiliary carry flag, the overflow flag, and the parity flag. Additionally, the PSW register contains the register bank select flags which are used to select which of the "R" register banks are currently selected.

PSW (program status word) register:

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The program status word (PSW) register is an 8-bit register. It is also referred to as the flag register.

7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
CY	AC	----	RS1	RS0	OV	----	P

CY: Carry-flag.

AC: Auxiliary carry-flag.

---- Available to the user for general-purpose.

RS1: register bank selector bit 1.

RS0: register bank selector bit 0.

OV: overflow flag.

---- User definable bit.

P: Parity flag. Set/cleared by hardware each instruction cycle to indicate an odd/even number of 1 bits in the accumulator.

Other SFRs:

The chart above is a summary of all the SFRs that exist in a standard 8051. All derivative microcontrollers of the 8051 must support these basic SFRs in order to maintain compatibility with the underlying MCS51 standard.

PIN DIAGRAM:

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1–8: (Port 1):

Each of these pins can be used as either input or output according to your needs. Also, pins 1 and 2 (P1.0 and P1.1) have special functions associated with Timer.

9: RESET SIGNAL:

High logical state on this input halts the MCU and clears all the registers. Bringing this pin back to logical state zero starts the program anew as if the power had just been turned on. In another words, positive voltage impulse on this pin resets the MCU. Depending on the device's purpose and environs, this pin is usually connected to the push-button, reset-upon-start circuit or a brown out reset circuit. The image shows one simple circuit for safe reset upon starting the controller. It is utilized in situations when power fails to reach its optimal voltage.

10-17:

Port 3 and Port 1, each of these pins can be used as universal input or output. However, each pin of Port 3 has an alternative function.

Beside its role as universal I/O port, each pin of Port 3 has an alternate function. In order to use one of these functions, the pin in question has to be designated as input, i.e. the appropriate bit of register P3 needs to be set. From a hardware standpoint, Port 3 is similar to Port 0.

As can be seen from the individual descriptions of the ports, they all share highly similar structure. However, you need to consider which task should be assigned to which port. For example: if utilizing port as output with high level (5V), avoid using Port 0, as its pins cannot produce high logical level without an additional resistor connected to +5V.

If using other port to a same end, bear in mind that built-in resistors have relatively high values, producing the currents limited to few hundreds of amperes as pin output.

Pin 10:

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RXD - serial input for asynchronous communication or serial output for synchronous communication.

Pin 11:

TXD - serial output for asynchronous communication or clock output for synchronous communication

Pin 12: INT0 - input for interrupt 0

Pin 13: INT1 - input for interrupt 1

Pin 14: T0 - clock input of counter 0

Pin 15: T1 - clock input of counter 1

Pin 16: WR - signal for writing to external (add-on) RAM memory

Pin 17: RD - signal for reading from external RAM memory.

18-19: X2 and X1;

X2 and X1 are input and output of internal oscillator. Quartz crystal controlling the frequency commonly connects to these pins. Capacitances within the oscillator mechanism (see the image) are not critical and are normally about 30pF. Instead of a quartz crystal, miniature ceramic resonators can be used for dictating the pace. In that case, manufacturers recommend using somewhat higher capacitances (about 47 pf). New capacitors works at frequencies from 0Hz to 50MHz.

20: GND: Ground

21- 28:

Port 2, if external memory is not present, pins of Port 2 act as universal input/output. If external memory is present, this is the location of the higher address byte, i.e. addresses A8 – A15. It is important to note that in cases when not all the 8 bits are used for addressing the memory (i.e. memory is smaller than 64kB), the rest of the unused bits are not available as input/output.

Intelligent Robot

When external memory is used, this port contains the higher address byte (addresses A8–A15), similar to Port 0. Otherwise, it can be used as universal I/O port.

29:

PSEN; MCU activates this bit (brings to low state) upon each reading of byte (instruction) from program memory. If external ROM is used for storing the program, PSEN is directly connected to its control pins.

Of the external memory, MCU sends the lower byte of the address register (addresses A0 – A7) to port P0 and activates the output ALE. External register (74HCT373 or 74HCT375 circuits are common), memorizes the state of port P0 upon receiving a signal from ALE pin, and uses it as part of the address for memory chip. During the second part of the mechanical MCU cycle, signal on ALE is off, and port P0 is used as *Data Bus*. In this way, by adding only one cheap integrated circuit, data from port can be multiplexed and the port simultaneously used for transferring both addresses and data.

31: EA:

Bringing this pin to the logical state zero (mass) designates the ports P2 and P3 for transferring addresses regardless of the presence of the internal memory. This means that even if there is a program loaded in the MCU it will not be executed, but the one from the external ROM will be used instead. Conversely, bringing the pin to the high logical state causes the controller to use both memories, first the internal, and then the external (if present).

32-39:

Port 0 Similar to Port 2, Port 0 has two-fold role if external memory is used, it contains the lower address byte (addresses A0-A7); otherwise all bits of the port are either input or output. Another feature of this port comes to play when it has been designated as output. Unlike other ports, Port 0 lacks the "pull up" resistor (resistor with +5V on one end). This seemingly insignificant change has the following consequences:

When designated as input, pin of Port 0 acts as high impedance offering the infinite input resistance with no "inner" voltage.

Intelligent Robot

When designated as output, pin acts as "open drain". Clearing a port bit grounds the appropriate pin on the case (0V). Setting a port bit makes the pin act as high impedance. Therefore, to get positive logic (5V) at output, external "pull up" resistor needs to be added for connecting the pin to the positive pole.

Therefore, to get one (5V) on the output, external "pull up" resistor needs to be added for connecting the pin to the positive pole.

40: VCC: Power +5V.

3.6 SERIAL COMMUNICATION:

When a microprocessor communicates with the outside world, it provides data in byte-sized chunks. In some cases, such as printers, the information is simply grabbed from the 8-bit data bus and presented to the 8-bit data bus of the printer. This can work only if the cable is not too long, since long cables diminish and even distort signals. Furthermore, an 8-bit data path is expensive. For these reasons, serial communication is used for transferring data between two systems located at distances of hundreds of feet to millions of miles apart.

The fact that in serial communication a single data line is used instead of the 8-bit data line of parallel communication makes it not only much cheaper but also makes it possible for two computers located in two different cities to communicate over the telephone.

Serial data communication uses two methods, a synchronous and asynchronous. The synchronous method transfers a block of data at a time while the asynchronous transfers a single byte at a time. It is mean possible to write software to use either of these methods, but the programs can be tedious and long. For this reason, there are special IC chips made by many manufacturers for serial data communications. These chips are commonly referred to as UART (universal asynchronous receiver-transmitter) and USART (universal synchronous -asynchronous receiver-transmitter). The 8051 chips has built-in UART, which is discussed

3.6.1 ASYNCHRONOUS SERIAL COMMUNICATION AND DATA FRAMING:

Transmitter and receiver do not explicitly coordinate each data transmission. Transmitter can wait arbitrarily long between transmissions. Used, for example, when transmitter such as a keyboard may not always have data ready to send Asynchronous may also mean no explicit information about where data bits begin and end The data coming in at the receiving end of the data line in a serial data transfer is all 0's and 1's; it is difficult to make sense of the data unless the sender and receiver agree on a set of rules, a protocol, on how the data is packed, how many bits constitute the character, and when the data begins and ends.

3.6.2 START AND STOP BITS:

A synchronous serial data communication is widely used for character orientation transmissions. In the asynchronous method, each character is placed in between start and stop bits. This is called framing. In data framing for asynchronous communications, the data, such as ASCII characters, are packed in between a start bit and a stop bits. The start bit is always one-bit but the stop bit can be one or two bits. If the transmitter and receiver are using different speeds, stop bit will not be received at the expected time problem is called framing error. The start bit is always a 0 and the stop bit is 1.

3.6.3 PARITY BIT:

In some systems in order to maintain data integrity, the parity bit of the character byte is included in the data frame. This means that for each character we have a single parity bit in addition to start and stop bits. The parity bit is odd or even. In case of an odd parity bit the number of data bits of a book of including the parity bit, is even.

3.6.4 DATA TRANSFER RATE:

The rate of data transfer in serial data communication is stated in bps (bits per second). Another widely used terminology for bps is baud rate. Baud rate is defined as the number of signal changes per second. As far as the conductor wire is concerned, the baud rates as bps are the same. If each signal change represents more than one bit, bits per second may be greater than baud rate.

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3.6.5 RS232 STANDARDS:

Two allow compatibility among the data communication equipment made by various manufacturers; an interfacing standard called RS232, was set by the electronics industries association (EIA) in 1960. RS 232 is the standard defined for the connection of "Data Terminal Equipment" (DTE) to "Data Communications Equipment" (DCE).

DTE (Data Terminal Equipment) is a generic term for an item which forms part of the "information processing" portions of a system. Examples are: computer, printer, and terminal.

DCE (Data Communications Equipment) is a device, which provides an interface between a DTE and a communications link.

3.7 INTERFACE FOR DTE/DCE CONNECTION:

All Signals Are "Ground Referenced" to in Pin 7

TXD, RXD---- Transmit and Receive Signal

RTS---- Request to Send, from DTE

CTS---- Clear to send, from DCE together with RTS

DTE---- Data Terminal Ready, indicates to the modem that a DTE is Connected and enabled.

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DSR--- Data Set Ready, indicates to the DTE that the modem is present and turned on
CD-- Carrier Detect indicates that this modem is receiving a signal from the remote modem.

In RS 232, a 1 is represented by -3 to -25V which is called Mark, while a 0 bit is +3 to +25V which is called Space. To connect any RS 232 to a μ c system, voltage converters such as Max 232 are used. Max 232 IC chips are commonly referred to as line drivers. 8.3. MAX 232. The RS 232 is not compatible with micro controllers, so a line driver converts the RS 232's signals to TTL voltage levels.

RS 232 WIRING AND CONNECTORS:

RS-232 Defines Serial, Asynchronous communication, Serial bits are encoded and transmitted one at a time. Asynchronous characters can be sent at any time and bits are not individually synchronized. This is standard for transfer of characters across copper wire.

3.8 FLOW CONTROL AND HARDWARE HANDSHAKING:

RTS/CTS: These signals are often now used to throttle the rate at which data is delivered between a DTE and modem: the DTE "drops" RTS when its buffers are nearly full, and the modem does the same using the CTS signal. This is nowadays referred to as "hardware handshaking".

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It's worth noting that modern high-speed modems almost universally use the RTS/CTS pair for this purpose. In fact, without hardware handshaking, data compression in modems would not be possible.

DTR/DSR and CD:

These signals are occasionally used in a similar way to RTS/CTS, particularly between computers and printers.

3.9 TESTING

3.9.1 PORT TESTING:

TO TEST THE 89C51 SYSTEM AND ITS PORTS:

Test the operation of the ports of your 89C51 trainer as follows. Assemble and run the test program below. The test program toggles the ports of the 89C51. Use a logic probe or the LED of your digital trainer to watch the bits of the ports toggle on and off. The time delay in between the "on" and "off" states is 1 second

```
/*program to test 89C51 ports*/  
    org 00h  
    mov a,#55h  
route: mov p0,a
```

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```
    mov p1,a
    mov p2,a
    call delay1sec
    cpl a
    jmp route
delay1sec: mov r3,#10
          again: mov r4,#200
          back:  mov r5,#250
          same:  djnz r5, same
                djnz r4,back
                djnz r3,again
          ret
          end
```

3.9.2 IMPLEMENTATION:

BASIC FORM OF ALP

3.9.3 BASIC FORM OF ASSEMBLY LANGUAGE PROGRAM:

Now that the basic form of an assembly language program has been given, the next question is: how it is created, assembled and made ready to run? The steps to create an executable assembly language program are outlined as follows.

1. First we use an editor to type in a program similar to program. Many excellent editors or word processors are available that can be used to create and/or edit the program. A widely used editor is the MS-DOS EDIT program (or notepad in Windows), which comes with all Microsoft operating systems. Notice that the editor must be able to produce an ASCII file. For many assemblers, the file names follow the usual DOS conventions, but the source file has the extension "ASM "or "SRC ", depending on which assembler you are using. Check your assembler for the convention. The "asm ", extension for the source file is used by an assembler in the next step.

2. The "ASM "source file containing the program code is created in step 1 is fed to an 8051 assembler. The assembler converts the instructions into machine code. The assembler will produce an object file and a list file. The extension for the object file is "OBJ "by the extension for the list file is "1ST ".

3. Assemblers require a third step calling linking. The link program takes one or more objects files and produces an absolute object file with the extension "ABS". 8051 trainers that have a monitor program use this ABS file.

4. Next the "ABS "file is fed into a program called "OH "(Object to Hex Converter) which creates a file with extension "HEX "that these ready to burn into ROM. This program comes with all 8051 assemblers. Recent Windows-based assemblers combine steps 2 through 4 into one step.

3.9.4 EVALUATION OF KEIL SOFTWARE:

1. Start the μ Vision Program

2. After the program has started:

Select File, New... from the program menu

Type your assembly file. The following is an example of a toggle program.

```
org 0H
mov A, #0ffH
route:
mov P1, A
acall delay1msec
cpl a
mov P2, a
acall delay1msec
sjmp route

delay1msec:
mov R3, #200
up: mov R2, #250
same: djnz R2, same
      djnz R3, up
      ret
      end
```

3. Select File, Save... from the program menu

The first time you save the program a dialog box will popup and allow you to name your file and file type.

Save program with filename: xxxxx.asm

The File type is mentioned at last (.asm) means assembly language

4. Select Project, New Project... from the program menu

Give some project name: xxxx.pro

5. Click on the Add button

A dialog-box appears, allowing you to add files to the project

Change the file type to Assembly.

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6. Select your assembly file.

Click on the Add button then close the Add dialog box.

7. Click on Save in your Project dialog box.
8. Select Project, Make: Build Project from the program menu

This creates the HEX file you need for the 8051

3.9.5 Using the Keil dScope Debugger

1. Select Run, dScope debugger... from the program menu

The debug program will start a new session

2. Select File, load CPU driver from the program menu

Choose the 8051.dll from the drop down list box; you can also select this directly.

3. Select File, load object file from the program menu.

Change the file type to HEX

Select your hex file, e.g. Toggle. Hex

Click OK

4. You should now see the source code of the file typed in earlier

5. Select Peripherals, I/O Ports from the program menu. so that you can see the how output varies on ports.

Select Port 0, Port 1, Port 2 and Port 3

6. Click on go to see the real time update of the I/O ports.

7. Click on stop when you are finished.

You can also single step through you program or set break points at locations that you want the debugger to stop at. To set a breakpoint, double click on the line.

4. METAL DETECTOR

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This circuit is most useful for security checking. Metal Detector available in the market is quite expensive.

This metal detector can be used to detect slightly big size metallic objects. It used a sensing Coil. This Coil should be kept near metallic objects for detection. Input of Circuit is a weak colpitt's R.F.range Oscillator. Sensing coil forms parts of tuned Oscillator.

When coil is brought near a metallic object magnetic energy is absorbed and Oscillator fails to work. Then final transistor conducts and buzzer is activated. Use a 9volts battery. After connecting battery adjust the 4.7k preset till circuit just stop sounding.

4.1 BLOCK DIAGRAM:

BLOCK DIAGRAM OF METAL DETECTOR

5. IR SENSOR

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In this application IR sensor has been introduced to detect the approaching obstacles to the robot. IR has been found very efficient cheaper one for short distance (of few meters) sensing purposes.

As shown here this circuit is using IR transmitter (any IR LED). IR LED is getting pulses from micro controller. The pulse train will be of 38 KHz for 600micro seconds of every 600micro seconds.

5.1 DESCRIPTION:

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The TSOP17... – Series are miniaturized receivers for infrared remote control systems. PIN diode and preamplifier are assembled on lead frame, the epoxy package is designed as IR filter. The demodulated output signal can directly be decoded by a microprocessor. TSOP17... Is the standard IR remote control receiver series, supporting all major transmission codes.

5.2 FEATURES:

- Photo detector and preamplifier in one package
- Internal filter for PCM frequency
- Improved shielding against electrical field disturbance
- TTL and CMOS compatibility
- Output active low
- Low power consumption
- High immunity against ambient light
- Continuous data transmission possible(up to 2400 bps)
- Suitable burst length .10 cycles/burst

5.3 BLOCK DIAGRAM:

The circuit of the TSOP17... is designed in that way that unexpected output pulses due to noise or disturbance signals are avoided. A band pass filter, an integrator stage and an automatic gain control are used to suppress such disturbances. The distinguishing mark between data signal and disturbance signal are carrier frequency, burst length and duty cycle.

The data signal should fulfill the following condition:

- Carrier frequency should be close to center frequency of the band pass (e.g. 38 kHz).
- Burst length should be 10 cycles/burst or longer.
- After each burst which is between 10 cycles and 70 cycles a gap time of at least 14 cycles is necessary.
- For each burst which is longer than 1.8ms a corresponding gap time is necessary at some time in the data stream. This gap time should have at least same length as the burst.
- Up to 1400 short bursts per second can be received continuously.

When a disturbance signal is applied to the TSOP17..it can still receive the data signal. However the sensitivity is reduced to that level that no unexpected pulses will occur.

5.4 OUTPUT FUNCTION:

6. Gas Sensor

Intelligent Robot

FEATURES

- * High sensitivity to alcohol and small sensitivity to Benzine .
- * Fast response and High sensitivity
- * Stable and long life
- * Simple drive circuit

APPLICATION

They are suitable for alcohol checker, Breathalyser.

SPECIFICATIONS

A. Standard work condition

Symbol	Parameter name	Technical condition	Remarks
V _c	Circuit voltage	5V±0.1	AC OR DC
V _H	Heating voltage	5V±0.1	AC OR DC
R _L	Load resistance	200KΩ	
R _H	Heater resistance	33Ω ±5%	Room Tem
P _H	Heating consumption	less than 750mw	

B. Environment condition

Symbol	Parameter name	Technical condition	Remarks
T _{ao}	Using Tem	-10℃-50℃	
T _{as}	Storage Tem	-20℃-70℃	
R _H	Related humidity	less than 95%Rh	
O ₂	Oxygen concentration	21%(standard condition) Oxygen concentration can affect sensitivity	minimum value is over 2%

C. Sensitivity characteristic

Symbol	Parameter name	Technical parameter	Remarks
R _s	Sensing Resistance	1MΩ-8 MΩ (0.4mg/L alcohol)	Detecting concentration scope: 0.05mg/L—10mg/L Alcohol
α (0.4/1 mg/L)	Concentration slope rate	≤0.6	
Standard detecting condition	Temp: 20℃ ±2℃ V _c :5V±0.1 Humidity: 65%±5% V _H : 5V±0.1		
Preheat time	Over 24 hour		

D. Structure and configuration, basic measuring circuit

Structure and configuration of MQ-3 gas sensor is shown as Fig. 1 (Configuration A or B), sensor composed by micro Al_2O_3 ceramic tube, Tin Dioxide (SnO_2) sensitive layer, measuring electrode and heater are fixed into a crust made by plastic and stainless steel net. The heater provides necessary work conditions for work of sensitive components. The enveloped MQ-3 have 6 pin , 4 of them are used to fetch signals, and other 2 are used for providing heating current.

Electric parameter measurement circuit is shown as Fig.2
 E. Sensitivity characteristic curve

Fig.2 sensitivity characteristics of the MQ-3

Fig.3 is shows the typical sensitivity characteristics of the MQ-3 for several gases. in their: Temp: 20°C、
 Humidity: 65%、
 O_2 concentration 21%
 $R_L=200k\Omega$
 R_o : sensor resistance at 0.4mg/L of Alcohol in the clean air.
 R_s : sensor resistance at various concentrations of gases.

Fig.4 is shows the typical dependence of the MQ-3 on temperature and humidity.
 R_o : sensor resistance at 0.4mg/L of Alcohol in air at 33%RH and 20 °C
 R_s : sensor resistance at 0.4mg/L of Alcohol at different temperatures and humidities.

SENSITIVITY ADJUSTMENT

Resistance value of MQ-3 is difference to various kinds and various concentration gases. So when using this components, sensitivity adjustment is very necessary. we recommend that you calibrate the detector for 0.4mg/L (approximately 200ppm) of Alcohol concentration in air and use value of Load resistance that(R_L) about 200 $K\Omega$ (100 $K\Omega$ to 470 $K\Omega$).

When accurately measuring, the proper alarm point for the gas detector should be determined after considering the temperature and humidity influence.

7. Temperature Sensor

FEATURES

- DS1631 and DS1631A Provide $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ Accuracy over a 0°C to $+70^{\circ}\text{C}$ Range
- DS1731 Provides $\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ Accuracy over a -10°C to $+85^{\circ}\text{C}$ Range
- DS1631A Automatically Begins Taking Temperature Measurements at Power-Up
- Operating Temperature Range: -55°C to $+125^{\circ}\text{C}$ (-67°F to $+257^{\circ}\text{F}$)
- Temperature Measurements Require No External Components
- Output Resolution is User-Selectable to 9, 10, 11, or 12 Bits
- Wide Power-Supply Range ($+2.7\text{V}$ to $+5.5\text{V}$)
- Converts Temperature-to-Digital Word in 750ms (max)
- Multidrop Capability Simplifies Distributed Temperature-Sensing Applications
- Thermostatic Settings are User-Definable and Nonvolatile (NV)
- Data is Read/Written Through 2-Wire Serial Interface (SDA and SCL Pins)
- All Three Devices are Available in 8-Pin μSOP Packages and the DS1631 is Also Available in a 150mil SO package—see Table 1 for Ordering Information

DESCRIPTION

The DS1631, DS1631A, and DS1731 digital thermometers provide 9, 10, 11, or 12-bit temperature readings over a -55°C to $+125^{\circ}\text{C}$ range. The DS1631 and DS1631A thermometer accuracy is $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ from 0°C to $+70^{\circ}\text{C}$ with $3.0\text{V} \leq V_{\text{DD}} \leq 5.5\text{V}$, and the DS1731 accuracy is $\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ from -10°C to $+85^{\circ}\text{C}$ with $3.0\text{V} \leq V_{\text{DD}} \leq 5.5\text{V}$. The thermostat on all three devices provides custom hysteresis with user-defined trip points (T_{H} and T_{L}). The T_{H} and T_{L} registers and thermometer configuration settings are stored in NV EEPROM so they can be programmed prior to installation. In addition, the DS1631A automatically begins taking temperature measurements at power-up, which allows it to function as a stand-alone thermostat. Communication with the DS1631/DS1631A/DS1731 is achieved through a 2-wire serial interface, and three address pins allow up to eight devices to be multidropped on the same 2-wire bus.

Pin descriptions for the DS1631/DS1631A/DS1731 are provided in Table 2 and user-accessible registers are summarized in Table 3. A functional diagram is shown in Figure 1.

PIN CONFIGURATIONS

See Table 2 for Pin Descriptions

APPLICATIONS

- Network Routers and Switches
- Cellular Base Stations
- Portable Products
- Any Space-Constrained Thermally Sensitive Product

Table 2. DETAILED PIN DESCRIPTION

PIN	SYMBOL	DESCRIPTION
1	SDA	Data Input/Output Pin for 2-Wire Serial Communication Port. Open-Drain.
2	SCL	Clock Input Pin for 2-Wire Serial Communication Port.
3	T _{OUT}	Thermostat Output Pin. Push-Pull.
4	GND	Ground Pin
5	A ₂	Address Input Pin
6	A ₁	Address Input Pin
7	A ₀	Address Input Pin
8	V _{DD}	Supply Voltage Pin. +2.7V to +5.5V Power-Supply Pin.

Figure 1. FUNCTIONAL DIAGRAM

ABSOLUTE MAXIMUM RATINGS*

Voltage on any Pin Relative to Ground	-0.5V to +6.0V
Operating Temperature Range	-55°C to +125°C
Storage Temperature Range	-55°C to +125°C
Solder Dip Temperature (10s)	See IPC/JEDEC J-STD-020A Specification
Reflow Oven Temperature	+220°C

* These are stress ratings only and functional operation of the device at these or any other conditions above those indicated in the operation sections of this specification is not implied. Exposure to absolute maximum rating conditions for extended periods of time may affect reliability.

DC ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISTICS

(V_{DD} = 2.7V to 5.5V; T_A = -55°C to +125°C.)

PARAMETER	SYMBOL	CONDITION	MIN	MAX	UNITS	NOTES
Supply Voltage	V _{DD}		2.7	5.5	V	1
DS1631, DS1631A Thermometer Error	T _{ERR}	0°C to +70°C, 3.0V ≤ V _{DD} ≤ 5.5V		±0.5	°C	2
		0°C to +70°C, 2.7V ≤ V _{DD} < 3.0V		±1		
		-55°C to +125°C		±2		
DS1731 Thermometer Error	T _{ERR}	-10°C to +85°C, 3.0V ≤ V _{DD} ≤ 5.5V		±1	°C	2
		-10°C to +85°C, 2.7V ≤ V _{DD} < 3.0V		±1.5		
		-55°C to +125°C		±2		
Low-Level Input Voltage	V _{IL}		-0.5	0.3 x V _{DD}	V	
High-Level Input Voltage	V _{IH}		0.7 x V _{DD}	V _{DD} + 0.3	V	
SDA Low-Level Output Voltage	V _{OL1}	3mA sink current	0	0.4	V	
	V _{OL2}	6mA sink current	0	0.6		
Input Current Each I/O Pin		0.4 < V _{IO} < 0.9V _{DD}	-10	+10	µA	
Active Supply Current	I _{DD}	Temperature conversion -55°C to +85°C		1	mA	3
		Temperature conversion +85°C to +125°C		1.25		
		E ² write		400	µA	
		Communication only		110		
Standby Supply Current	I _{STBY}	0°C to +70°C		800	nA	4
T _{OUT} Output Logic Voltage	V _{OH}	1mA source current	2.4		V	1
	V _{OL}	4mA sink current		0.4	V	1

Table 3. REGISTER SUMMARY

REGISTER NAME (USER ACCESS)	SIZE (BYTES)	MEMORY TYPE	REGISTER CONTENTS AND POWER-UP STATE
Temperature (Read Only)	2	SRAM	Measured temperature in two's complement format. Power-up state: -60°C (1100 0100 0000 0000)
T _H (Read/Write)	2	EEPROM	Upper alarm trip point in two's complement format. Power-up state: user defined.
T _L (Read/Write)	2	EEPROM	Lower alarm trip point in two's complement format. Power-up state: user defined.
Configuration (Various bits are Read/Write and Read Only—See Table 5)	1	SRAM, EEPROM	Configuration and status information. Unsigned data. 6 MSBs = SRAM 2 LSBs (POL and 1SHOT bits) = EEPROM Power-up state: 100011XX (XX = user defined)

OPERATION—MEASURING TEMPERATURE

The DS1631, DS1631A, and DS1731 measure temperature using bandgap-based temperature sensors. A delta-sigma analog-to-digital converter (ADC) converts the measured temperature to a 9-, 10-, 11-, or 12-bit (user-selectable) digital value that is calibrated in °C; for °F applications a lookup table or conversion routine must be used. Throughout this data sheet, the term “conversion” is used to refer to the entire temperature measurement and ADC sequence.

The DS1631 and DS1731 always power-up in a low-power idle state, and the Start Convert T command must be used to initiate conversions. The DS1631A always begins conversions automatically at power-up.

The DS1631, DS1631A, and DS1731 can be programmed to perform continuous consecutive conversions (continuous-conversion mode) or to perform single conversions on command (one-shot mode). The conversion mode is programmed through the 1SHOT bit in the configuration register as explained in the *CONFIGURATION REGISTER* section of this data sheet. In continuous-conversion mode, the DS1631A begins performing continuous conversions immediately at power-up, and the DS1631 and DS1731 begin continuous conversions after a Start Convert T command is issued. For all three devices, consecutive conversions continue to be performed until a Stop Convert T command is issued, at which time the device goes into a low-power idle state. Continuous conversions can be restarted at any time using the Start Convert T command.

In one-shot mode the DS1631A performs a single conversion at power-up, and the DS1631 and DS1731 perform a single temperature conversion when a Start Convert T command is issued. For all three devices, when the conversion is complete the device enters a low-power idle state and remains in that state until a single temperature conversion is again initiated by a Start Convert T command.

The resolution of the output digital temperature data is user-configurable to 9, 10, 11, or 12 bits, corresponding to temperature increments of 0.5°C, 0.25°C, 0.125°C, and 0.0625°C, respectively. The default resolution at power-up is 12 bits, and it can be changed through the R0 and R1 bits in the configuration register. Note that the conversion time doubles for each additional bit of resolution.

After each conversion, the digital temperature is stored as a 16-bit two's complement number in the two-byte temperature register as shown in Figure 4. The sign bit (S) indicates if the temperature is positive or negative: for positive numbers S = 0 and for negative numbers S = 1. The Read Temperature command

provides user access to the temperature register. Bits 3 through 0 of the temperature register are hardwired to 0. When the device is configured for 12-bit resolution, the 12 MSBs (bits 15 through 4) of the temperature register contain temperature data. For 11-bit resolution, the 11 MSBs (bits 15 through 5) of the temperature register contain data, and bit 4 is 0. Likewise, for 10-bit resolution, the 10 MSBs (bits 15 through 6) contain data, and for 9-bit the 9 MSBs (bits 15 through 7) contain data, and all unused LSBs contain 0s. Table 4 gives examples of 12-bit resolution output data and the corresponding temperatures.

Figure 4. TEMPERATURE, T_H, AND T_L REGISTER FORMAT

	bit 15	bit 14	bit 13	bit 12	bit 11	bit 10	bit 9	bit 8
MS Byte	S	2 ⁶	2 ⁵	2 ⁴	2 ³	2 ²	2 ¹	2 ⁰
	bit 7	bit 6	bit 5	bit 4	bit 3	bit 2	bit 1	bit 0
LS Byte	2 ⁻¹	2 ⁻²	2 ⁻³	2 ⁻⁴	0	0	0	0

Table 4. 12-BIT RESOLUTION TEMPERATURE/DATA RELATIONSHIP

TEMPERATURE (°C)	DIGITAL OUTPUT (BINARY)	DIGITAL OUTPUT (HEX)
+125	0111 1101 0000 0000	7D00h
+25.0625	0001 1001 0001 0000	1910h
+10.125	0000 1010 0010 0000	0A20h
+0.5	0000 0000 1000 0000	0080h
0	0000 0000 0000 0000	0000h
-0.5	1111 1111 1000 0000	FF80h
-10.125	1111 0101 1110 0000	F5E0h
-25.0625	1110 0110 1111 0000	E6F0h
-55	1100 1001 0000 0000	C900h

OPERATION—THERMOSTAT FUNCTION

The thermostat output (T_{OUT}) is updated after every temperature conversion, based on a comparison between the measured digital temperature and user-defined upper and lower thermostat trip points. T_{OUT} remains at the updated value until the next conversion completes. When the measured temperature meets or exceeds the value stored in the upper trip-point register (T_H), T_{OUT} becomes active and remains active until the measured temperature falls below the value stored in the lower trip-point register (T_L) (see Figure 5). This allows the user to program any amount of hysteresis into the output response. The active state of T_{OUT} is user-programmable through the polarity bit (POL) in the configuration register.

The user-defined values in the T_H and T_L registers (see Figure 4) must be in two’s complement format with the MSb (bit 15) containing the sign bit (S). The T_H and T_L resolution is determined by the R0 and R1 bits in the configuration register (see Table 6), so the T_H and T_L resolution matches the output temperature resolution. For example, for 10-bit resolution bits 5 through 0 of the T_H and T_L registers read out as 0 (even if 1s are written to these bits), and the converted temperature is compared to the 10 MSBs of T_H and T_L.

The T_H and T_L registers are stored in EEPROM; therefore, they are NV and can be programmed prior to device installation. Writing to and reading from the T_H and T_L registers is achieved using the Access TH

and Access TL commands. When making changes to the T_H and T_L registers, conversions should first be stopped using the Stop Convert T command if the device is in continuous conversion mode. Note that if the thermostat function is not used, the T_H and T_L registers can be used as general-purpose NV memory.

Another thermostat feature is the temperature high and low flags (THF and TLF) in the configuration register. These bits provide a record of whether the temperature has been greater than T_H or less than T_L at anytime since the device was powered up. These bits power up as 0s, and if the temperature ever exceeds the T_H register value, the THF bit is set to 1, or if the temperature ever falls below the T_L value, the TLF bit is set to 1. Once THF and/or TLF has been set, it remains set until overwritten with a 0 by the user or until the power is cycled.

DS1631A STAND-ALONE THERMOSTAT OPERATION

Since the DS1631A automatically begins taking temperature measurements at power-up, it can function as a standalone thermostat (i.e., it can provide thermostatic operation without microcontroller communication). For standalone operation, the NV T_H and T_L registers and the POL and 1SHOT bits in the configuration register should be programmed to the desired values prior to installation. Since the default conversion resolution at power-up is 12 bits ($R1 = 1$ and $R0 = 1$ in the configuration register), the conversion resolution is always 12 bits during standalone thermostat operation.

Figure 5. THERMOSTAT OUTPUT OPERATION

CONFIGURATION REGISTER

The configuration register allows the user to program various DS1631 options such as conversion resolution, T_{OUT} polarity, and operating mode. It also provides information to the user about conversion status, EEPROM activity, and thermostat activity. The configuration register is arranged as shown in Figure 6 and detailed descriptions of each bit are provided in Table 5. This register can be read from and written to using the Access Config command. When writing to the configuration register, conversions should first be stopped using the Stop Convert T command if the device is in continuous conversion mode. Note that the POL and 1SHOT bits are stored in EEPROM so they can be programmed prior to installation is desired. All other configuration register bits are SRAM and power up in the state shown in Table 5.

Figure 6. CONFIGURATION REGISTER

MSb	bit 6	bit 5	bit 4	bit 3	bit 2	bit 1	LSb
DONE	THF	TLF	NVB	R1	R0	POL*	1SHOT*

*NV (EEPROM)

2-WIRE SERIAL DATA BUS

The DS1631, DS1631A, and DS1731 communicate over a bidirectional 2-wire serial data bus that consists of a serial clock (SCL) signal and serial data (SDA) signal. The DS1631, DS1631A, and DS1731 interface to the bus through their SCL input pins and open-drain SDA I/O pins.

The following terminology is used to describe 2-wire communication:

Master Device: Microprocessor/microcontroller that controls the slave devices on the bus. The master device generates the SCL signal and START and STOP conditions.

Slave: All devices on the bus other than the master. The DS1631, DS1631A, and DS1731 always function as slaves.

Bus Idle or Not Busy: Both SDA and SCL remain high. SDA is held high by a pullup resistor when the bus is idle, and SCL must either be forced high by the master (if the SCL output is push-pull) or pulled high by a pullup resistor (if the SCL output is open-drain).

Transmitter: A device (master or slave) that is sending data on the bus.

Receiver: A device (master or slave) that is receiving data from the bus.

START Condition: Signal generated by the master to indicate the beginning of a data transfer on the bus. The master generates a START condition by pulling SDA from high to low while SCL is high (see Figure 8). A “repeated” START is sometimes used at the end of a data transfer (instead of a STOP) to indicate that the master will perform another operation.

STOP Condition: Signal generated by the master to indicate the end of a data transfer on the bus. The master generates a STOP condition by transitioning SDA from low to high while SCL is high (see Figure 8). After the STOP is issued, the master releases the bus to its idle state.

Acknowledge (ACK): When a device is acting as a receiver, it must generate an acknowledge (ACK) on the SDA line after receiving every byte of data. The receiving device performs an ACK by pulling the SDA line low for an entire SCL period (see Figure 8). During the ACK clock cycle, the transmitting device must release SDA. A variation on the ACK signal is the “not acknowledge” (NACK). When the master device is acting as a receiver, it uses a NACK instead of an ACK after the last data byte to indicate that it is finished receiving data. The master indicates a NACK by leaving the SDA line high during the ACK clock cycle.

Slave Address: Every slave device on the bus has a unique 7-bit address that allows the master to access that device. The 7-bit bus address is 1 0 0 1 A₂ A₁ A₀, where A₂, A₁, and A₀ are user-selectable through the corresponding input pins. The three address pins allow up to eight DS1631s, DS1631As, or DS1731s to be multidropped on the same bus.

Control Byte: The control byte is transmitted by the master and consists of the 7-bit slave address plus a read/write (R/W) bit (see Figure 7). If the master is going to read data from the slave device then R/W = 1, and if the master is going to write data to the slave device then R/W = 0.

Command Byte: The command byte can be any of the command protocols described in the *COMMAND SET* section of this data sheet.

Figure 7. CONTROL BYTE

bit 7	bit 6	bit 5	bit 4	bit 3	bit 2	bit 1	bit 0
1	0	0	1	A ₂	A ₁	A ₀	R/W

2-WIRE READS

The master can read data from the DS1631/DS1631A/DS1731 by issuing an Access Config, Access TH, Access TL, or Read Temperature command following the control byte (see Figures 9c and 9e). After receiving an ACK in response to the command, the master must generate a repeated START followed by a control byte with the same slave address as the first control byte. However, this time the R/W bit must be a 1, which tells the DS1631/DS1631A/DS1731 that a “read” is being performed. After the DS1631/DS1631A/DS1731 send an ACK in response to this control byte, it begins transmitting the requested data on the next clock cycle. One byte of data will be transmitted when reading from the configuration register after which the master must respond with a NACK followed by a STOP. For two-byte reads (i.e., from the Temperature, T_H , or T_L register), the master must respond to the first data byte with an ACK and to the second byte with a NACK followed by a STOP. If only the most significant byte of data is needed, the master can issue a NACK followed by a STOP after reading the first data byte.

COMMAND SET

The DS1631/DS1631A/DS1731 command set is detailed below:

Start Convert T [51h]

Initiates temperature conversions. If the part is in one-shot mode (1SHOT = 1), only one conversion is performed. In continuous mode (1SHOT = 0), continuous temperature conversions are performed until a Stop Convert T command is issued.

Stop Convert T [22h]

Stops temperature conversions when the device is in continuous conversion mode (1SHOT = 0).

Read Temperature [AAh]

Reads last converted temperature value from the 2-byte temperature register.

Access TH [A1h]

Reads or writes the 2-byte T_H register.

Access TL [A2h]

Reads or writes the 2-byte T_L register.

Access Config [ACh]

Reads or writes the 1-byte configuration register.

Software POR [54h]

Initiates a software power-on-reset (POR), which stops temperature conversions and resets all registers and logic to their power-up states. The software POR allows the user to simulate cycling the power without actually powering down the device.

8. LIQUID CRYSTAL DISPLAY [LCD]

As in recent years the LCD is finding widespread use replacing LED this is due to the following reasons:

- The declining prices of LCD
- The ability to display numbers, characters and graphics. This is in contrast to LED, which are limited to numbers and a few characters.
- Incorporation refreshing controller into the LCD, there by the easy relieving the CPU of the task of refreshing the LCD. In contrast, the CPU, to keep the data displaying, must refresh the LED.
- Ease of programming for characters and graphics.

8.1 LCD PIN DESCRIPTIONS:

LCD has 14 pins. The function of each pin is given shows the positions for various LCD.

VCC, VSS and VEE:

While VCC and VSS provide + 5 V and ground respectively, VEE is used for controlling LCD contrast.

RS, REGISTER SELECT:

There are two very important registers inside LCD. The RS pin is used for their selection as follows. Is $RS=0$, the instruction command code register is selected, allowing the user to send a command such as clear display, Cursor at home, etc. if $RS=1$ the data register is selected, allowing the user to send data to be displayed on the LCD.

R/W, READ/WRITE:

R/W input allows the user to write information into the LCD or read information from it. R/W=1 when reading; R/W=0 when writing.

E, ENABLE:

The LCD to latch information presented to its data pins uses the enable pin. When data is supplied to data pins, a high to low pulse must be applied to this pin in order for the LCD to latch in the data present at the data pins. This pulse must be a minimum of 450 ns wide.

D0-D7:

The 8-bit data pins, D0-D7, are used to send information to the LCD or read the content of the LCD internal registers.

To display letters and numbers, we send ASCII codes for the letters A-Z, a-z, and numbers 0-9 to these pins while making RS=1. We also use RS=0 to check the busy flag bit to see if the LCD ready to receive. The busy flag is D7 and can be read when R/W=1 and RS=0, as follows: if R/w=1 and RS = 0. When D7 =1, the LCD is busy taking care of internal operations and will not accept any new information. When D7=0, the LCD is ready to receive new information.

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CODE	COMMAND TO LCD INSTRUCTION
1	Clear display screen
2	Return home
4	Decrement cursor (shift cursor to left)
6	Increment cursor (shift cursor to right)
5	Shift Display right
7	Shift display left
8	Display off, cursor off
A	Display off, cursor on
C	Display on, cursor off
E	Display on, cursor blinking
F	Display on, cursor blinking
10	Shift cursor position to left
14	Shift cursor position to right
18	Shift the entire display to the left
1C	Shift the entire display to the right
80	Force cursor to beginning of 1 st line
C0	Force cursor to beginning of 2 nd line
38	2 lines and 5x7 matrix

9. 74LS374 (LATCH)

This is an Octal D-type edge triggered flip flops comprising of 8 D-type flip flops in a single package and also 3-STATE bus-driving outputs. Data is loaded through parallel-access for loading. These 8-bit registers feature totem-pole 3-STATE outputs designed specifically for driving highly capacitive or relatively low-impedance loads. The high-impedance state and increased high-logic level drive provide these registers with the capability of being connected directly to and driving the bus lines in a bus-organized system without need for interface or pull-up components. They are particularly attractive for implementing buffer registers, I/O ports, bi-directional bus drivers, and working registers.

The eight latches of the 74LS374 are edge triggered D-type flip-flops. The operations of a D flip-flop are much simpler. It has only one input addition to the clock. It is very useful when a single data bit (0 or 1) is to be stored. If there is a HIGH on the D

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input when a clock pulse is applied, the flip-flop Sets and stores a 1. If there is a LOW on the D input when a clock pulse is applied, the flip-flop RESETS and stores a 0. The truth table below summarizes the operations of the positive edge-triggered D flip-flop. As before, the negative edge-triggered flip-flop works the same except that the falling edge of the clock pulse is the triggering edge. The eight latches of the 74LS374 are transparent D-type latches meaning that while the enable (G) is high the Q outputs will follow the data (D) inputs. When the enable is taken low the output will be latched at the level of the data that was set up.

A buffered output control unit can be used to place the eight outputs in either a normal logic state (high or low levels) or a high impedance state. In the high-impedance state the outputs neither load nor drive the bus lines significantly. The output control does not affect the internal operation of the latches or flip-flops. That is, the old data can be retained or new data can be entered even while the outputs are off. As this is having P-N-P inputs, these reduce DC loading on data lines.

9.1 PIN DIAGRAM:

9.2 PIN DESCRIPTION (Hc374):

PIN No	SYMBOL	NAME AND FUNCTION
1	\overline{OE}	3 State output Enable Input (Active LOW)
2, 5, 6, 9, 12, 15, 16, 19	Q0 to Q7	3 State outputs
3, 4, 7, 8, 13, 14, 17, 18	D0 to D7	Data Inputs
11	CLOCK	Clock Input (LOW to HIGH, edge triggered)
10	GND	Ground (0V)
20	V _{CC}	Positive Supply Voltage

9.3 TRUTH TABLE:

INPUTS			OUTPUTS	
\overline{OE}	CK	D	Q (HC374)	\overline{Q} (HC534)
H	X	X	Z	Z
L		X	NO CHANGE	NO CHANGE
L		L	L	H
L		H	H	L

9.4 LOGIC DIAGRAM:

10. MOTOR DRIVER (STA401A)

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It is used to amplify the signal. It is a Darlington transistor with built-in avalanche diode.

The equivalent circuit diagram

Darlington transistors are circuits that combine two bipolar transistors in a single device. They provide high current gain and require less space than configurations that use two discrete transistors.

In Darlington pairs, transistor collectors are tied together and the emitter of the first transistor is directly coupled to the base of the second transistor. The total gain, which is often 1000 or more, is the product of the gain of the individual transistors. Compared to single transistor configurations, Darlington transistor pairs have more phase shift at high frequencies and can become unstable with negative feedback more easily.

Darlington transistors also have a higher base-emitter voltage, which is the sum of both base emitter voltages. NPN is a physical bipolar junction transistor (BJT) arrangement in which the emitter and the collector are made of N-type material and the base is made of P-type material.

11. Stepper Motor

Stepping motors fill a unique niche in the motor control world. These motors are commonly used in measurement and control applications. Sample applications include ink jet printers, CNC machines and volumetric pumps. Several features common to all stepper motors make them ideally suited for these types of applications.

11.1 FEATURES:

Brush less - Stepper motors are brush less. The Commutator and brushes of conventional motors are some of the most failure-prone components, and they create electrical arcs that are undesirable or dangerous in some environments.

Load Independent - Stepper motors will turn at a set speed regardless of load as long as the load does not exceed the torque rating for the motor.

Open Loop Positioning - Stepper motors move in quantified increments or steps. As long as the motor runs within its torque specification, the position of the shaft is known at all times without the need for a feedback mechanism.

Holding Torque - Stepper motors are able to hold the shaft stationary.

Excellent response: To start-up, stopping and reverse.

11.2 TYPES OF STEPPING MOTORS:

There are three basic types of stepping motors: permanent magnet, variable reluctance and hybrid. This application note covers all three types. Permanent magnet motors have a magnetized rotor, while variable reluctance motors have toothed soft-iron rotors.

Stepping motors combine aspects of both permanent magnet and variable reluctance technology. The stator or stationary part of the stepping holds multiple windings. The arrangement of windings is the primary factor that distinguishes different

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types of stepping motors from an electrical point of view. From the electrical and control system perspective, variable reluctance motors are from the other, types. Both permanent magnet hybrid motors may be wound using either unipolar windings, bipolar windings or bifilar windings.

11.3 CHOOSING A MOTOR:

There are several factors to take into consideration when choosing a stepping motor for an application. Some of these factors are what type of motor to use, the torque requirements of the system, the complexity of the controller, as well as the physical characteristics of the motor. The following paragraphs discuss these considerations.

FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS:

Even when the type of motor is determined, there are still several decisions to be made before selecting one particular motor. Torque, operating environment, longevity, physical size, step size, maximum RPM these are some of the factors that will influence which motor is chosen.

STEP SIZE:

One of the most crucial decisions to make is the step size of the motor. This will be determined by the resolution necessary for a particular application. The most common step sizes for PM motors are 7.5 and 3.6 degrees. This corresponds to 48 and 100 steps per revolution respectively. Hybrid motors typically have step sizes ranging from 3.6 degrees (100 steps per revolution) to 0.9 degrees (400 steps per revolution). Some stepping motors are sold with gear reductions, which provide smaller step angles than are possible with even the finest stepping motors. Gear reductions also increase the available torque, but because torque falls with stepping rate, they decrease the maximum rotational speed. For linear movement, many stepper motors are coupled to a lead screw by a nut (these motors are also known as linear actuators). Even coarse steps with this arrangement translate to very fine movements of the lead screw because of the gear reduction inherent to this mechanism.

TORQUE:

Torque is a critical consideration when choosing stepping motor. Stepper motors have different types of rated torque. These are:

- Holding torque - The torque required to rotate the motor's shaft while the windings are energized.
- Pull-in torque - The torque against which a motor can accelerate from a standing start without missing any steps, when driven at a constant stepping rate.
- Pull-out torque - The load a motor can move when at operating speed.
- Detent torque - The torque required to rotate the motor's shaft while the windings are not energized.

11.4 UNIPOLAR STEPPER MOTOR:

Unipolar stepping motors are composed of two windings, each with a center tap. The center taps are either brought outside the motor as two separate wires or connected to each other internally and brought outside the motor as one wire. As a result, unipolar motors have 5 or 6 wires. Regardless of the number of wires, unipolar motors are driven in the same way. The center tap wire is tied to a power supply and the ends of the coils are alternatively grounded.

Unipolar stepping motors are made of permanent magnet and hybrid motors, operates differently from variable reluctance motors. Rather than operating by minimizing the length of the flux path between the stator poles and these rotor teeth, where the direction of current flow through the stator windings is irrelevant, these motors operate by attracting the north or south poles of the permanently magnetized rotor to the stator poles. Thus, in the motors, the direction of the current through the stator windings determines which rotor poles will be attracted to which stator poles. Current direction in the unipolar motors is dependent on which half of the winding is energized. Physically, the halves of the winding are wound parallel to one another. Therefore, one winding acts as either a north or south poles depending on which half is powered.

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The figure shows the cross section of a 30 Degrees for step unipolar motor. Motor primary winding is distributed between the top and bottom stator poles. While motor secondary winding is distributed between the left and the right motor poles. The rotor is a permanent magnet with six poles, three north and three south as shown in figure

Fig: Unipolar Stepper Motor

The difference between a permanent magnet stepping motor and a hybrid stepping motor lies in the construction of multi pole rotor and multi-pole stator.

EXAMPLE:

Note: Only half of each winding is energized at a time in the above sequence. As above, the following sequence will spin the motor clockwise 12 steps or one revolution.

Winding 1a: 100010001000

Winding 1b: 001000100010

Winding 2a: 010001000100

Winding 2b: 000100010001

Time

Winding 1a: 110011001100

Winding 1b: 001100110011

Winding 2a: 011001100110

Winding 2b: 100110011001

Time

Unlike in the first sequence described, two windings are energized at one time in the second sequence. This gives the motor more torque, but increases the power usage by the motor. Each of above sequences describes single stepping the motor in its rated step size (in this case degree). Combining these two sequences allows half stepping the motor. The combined sequence is shown in Example (24 steps per revolution).

11.5 UNIPOLAR MOTOR CONTROL CIRCUIT:

The basic control circuit for a unipolar motor, shown in Figure, is similar to that for a variable reluctance motor. Note the extra diodes across each of the MOSFET's. These are necessary because the inductor is center tapped in unipolar motors. When one end of the motor winding is pulled down the other end will rise and visa versa. These diodes prevent the voltage from falling below ground across the MOSFET's. Some MOSFET's have integral diodes that allow reverse current to flow unimpeded, regardless of the gate voltage. If such transistors are used, and if these integral diodes have sufficient current carrying capacity carry the full motor current, the lower diodes shown in Figure 8 can be omitted. All of the diodes must have switching speeds comparable to the speed of the transistors.

Stepper motors are ideally suited for measurement and control applications. The step resolution and performance of these motors can be improved through a technique called micro stepping. Stepping motor performance can also be improved by driving these motors at a voltage greater than what they are rated for. If higher voltage is used to boost performance, then current-limiting considerations must be taken into account.

12. SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

In any embedded systems application development life cycle one has to adopt one of the finest hierarchical approach. This approach directly influences the development productivity. Because of one is dealing with both hardware and software and vast comprehensibility the development process is very complex.

The developer's job becomes easy when necessary soft wares to carry out many phases of development. This is given in the line diagram.

Integrated Development Environment is the first necessity. The IDE is user friendly software in which one can write the program and see it's out come. The IDE will be equipped with many other tools. In this application Keil micro vision 2 IDE has been used.

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12.1 Cross compiler:

This tool is required to build, if user adopts high level language for his application development. Cross compiler converts source code into the instructions of the target controller. The output of the cross compiler is given to the assembler. Since it is the programmers choice to go to high level languages Keil offers C51 as the cross compiler it compiles only Embedded C code not other like Embedded C++ and Embedded Java.

12.2 Assembler:

This tool takes instructions and converts into operation code of the target controller. This process is quite lengthy and carried out phase by phase. Assembler is the combination of debugger, linker and loader. In Keil we have A51 assembler to build our assembly language code.

12.3 Debugger:

As its name itself indicates it is for fixing the bugs that is all syntax errors from the code. Once the code is free from bugs it will be passed to liker.

12.4 Linker:

Linking operations like attaching starting address of a subroutine to the main program will be done by liker. It creates an absolute sequential code which is to be executed.

12.5 Loader:

It simply takes liked file and converts into hex code which can be downloaded into the micro controller.

All debugger, liker and loader are the part of assembler software.

12.6 Simulator:

Once the code is ready then it is always not a good idea to dump into micro controller. First it has to be tested in IDE. The tool provided by an IDE which shows an exact replica of micro controller's perception is nothing but simulator.

13. CODE SHEET

```

/*-----Code Sheet-----*/
/*-----Bluetooth Robot Control--Kit-----*/
/*---06th March 2008 -----* M I C TECH CENTRE *-----*/
/*-----*_*_*_*-----Port Equalizations-----*_*_*_*-----*/

```

MOTOR_PORT	EQU	P2	
MOTOR_EN	EQU	P1.4	
LCD_PORT	EQU	P0	
LCD_RS	EQU	P1.5	
LCD_RW	EQU	P1.6	
LCD_EN	EQU	P1.7	
FrLEDrt	EQU	p1.0	
FrLEDlt	EQU	p1.1	
BkLEDrt	EQU	p1.2	
BkLEDlt	EQU	p1.3	
Tempr_SDA	EQU	P3.6	; Temp. Sensor - Data (in/out)
Tempr_SCL	EQU	P3.7	; Temp. Sensor - Data Clock
StartConv	EQU	51h	; initiates temp. conversions
STOP_CONV	EQU	22h	; stops temp. conversions
Read_Tempr	EQU	0AAh	; reads last converted temp.
ACCESS_TH	EQU	0A1h	
ACCESS_TL	EQU	0A2h	
ACCESS_CONFIG	EQU	0ACh	
CNTR_WRD_WRITE	EQU	90H	
CNTR_WRD_READ	EQU	91H	
MAX_TEMP	EQU	28H	
MIN_TEMP	EQU	0AH	
SOFTWARE_POR	EQU	54h	
CONFIG_REG	EQU	00001110b	; Setting for 12bit resolution with Tout +ve polarity
Smoke_Bit	EQU	P3.4	

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/*-----Assigning memory location-----*/

FORW_BIT	BIT	10H
REV_BIT	BIT	11H
LEF_BIT	BIT	12H
RIG_BIT	BIT	13H
STP_BIT	BIT	14H
OBS_BIT	BIT	15H
MET_BIT	BIT	16H
BT_MODE	BIT	17H
DIS_BIT	BIT	18H
TEMP_BIT	BIT	19H
GAS_BIT	BIT	1AH
FBTxOk	BIT	1BH

/*-----User defined memory-----*/

TEMP_1	DATA	70H
TEMP_2	DATA	71H
TEMP_3	DATA	72H
DelayC1	DATA	7BH
DelayC2	DATA	7CH
DelayC3	DATA	7DH
TEMP_MSB	DATA	77H
TEMP_LSB	DATA	78H
READ_CONFIG	DATA	79H

/*-----Beginning of the Program-----*/

```
ORG 0000H
SJMP POWER_ON
```

/*-----IR Sensor Obstacle Interrupt-----*/

```
ORG 0003H
CALL OBS_ISR
RETI
```

/*-----Smoke Sensor Interrupt-----*/

```
ORG 000BH
CALL TIMER0_ISR
RETI
```

Intelligent Robot

/*-----Metal Detector Interrupt-----*/

```
ORG 0013H
CALL MET_ISR
RETI
```

/*-----Serial Communication Interrupt-----*/

```
ORG 0023H
CALL SRL_ISR
RETI
```

/*-----Main Program-----*/

```
ORG 0050H

POWER_ON:  MOV MOTOR_PORT,#00H
           CALL LATCH_EN
           MOV IE,#00H
           CLR FORW_BIT
           CLR REV_BIT
           CLR LEF_BIT
           CLR RIG_BIT
           CLR STP_BIT
           CLR OBS_BIT
           CLR MET_BIT
           CLR TEMP_BIT
           CLR BT_MODE
           CALL LCD_INIT
           CALL WELCOME_NOTE
           CALL DELAY5SEC
           CALL TEMP_INIT
           CALL LCD_CLEAR
```

/*-----Serial Communication Initialization-----*/

```
MOV TMOD,#21H
MOV TH1,#-6
MOV SCON,#50H
MOV IE,#90H
SETB TR1
```

```
Clr  FBTxOk
CALL BT_INIT ; Very Imp
```

Intelligent Robot

```
CALL LCD_CLEAR
CALL DISPLINE3
MOV DPTR,#CONN_OK
CALL DISP_LCD
```

```
MOV DPTR,#SND_ROT
CALL BT_TX
```

```
MOV DPTR,#TEMPR
CALL BT_TX
```

```
MOV IE,#97H
SETB IT0
SETB IT1
SETB TR0
```

```
CLR FORW_BIT
CLR REV_BIT
CLR LEF_BIT
CLR RIG_BIT
CLR STP_BIT
```

```
CLR OBS_BIT
CLR MET_BIT
CLR TEMP_BIT
CLR GAS_BIT
```

/*-----Main Loop of the Program after Bluetooth device is Connected-----*/

```
MAINLOOP:    Cpl   FrLEDlt
             Cpl   BkLEDrt
             JNB   FORW_BIT,NO_FORW
             CALL  FORWARD
```

```
NO_FORW:    JNB   REV_BIT,NO_REV
             CALL  REVERSE
```

```
NO_REV:     JNB   LEF_BIT,NO_LEFT
             CALL  LEFT
```

```
NO_LEFT:    JNB   RIG_BIT,NO_RIG
             CALL  RIGHT
```

```
NO_RIG:     JNB   STP_BIT,NO_STP
             CLR   STP_BIT
             CALL  STOP
```

Intelligent Robot

```
NO_STP:      JNB  GAS_BIT,NO_Smoke
             Clr  GAS_BIT
             Call Smoke_Detect
```

```
NO_Smoke:   JNB  MET_BIT,NO_MET
             CLR  MET_BIT
             CALL Metal_Detect
```

```
NO_MET:     JNB  OBS_BIT,NO_OBS
             CLR  OBS_BIT
             CALL OBS_Detect
```

```
NO_OBS:     Cpl  FrLEDrt
             Cpl  BkLEDlt
             JNB  TEMP_BIT,NO_TEMP
             CLR  TEMP_BIT
             CALL READ_TEMP
             CALL DISPLAY_TEMP
```

```
NO_TEMP:    CALL DELAY10MS
             JMP  MAINLOOP
```

/*-----Robot Direction Control Decision-----*/

```
SET_DIR:    MOV  A,R7
             CJNE A,#"8",FORW_NOT
             CLR  TEMP_BIT
             SETB FORW_BIT
             CLR  REV_BIT
             CLR  LEF_BIT
             CLR  RIG_BIT
             CLR  STP_BIT
             CLR  OBS_BIT
             CLR  MET_BIT
             RET
```

```
FORW_NOT:   CJNE A,#"2",REV_NOT
             CLR  TEMP_BIT
             CLR  FORW_BIT
             SETB REV_BIT
             CLR  LEF_BIT
             CLR  RIG_BIT
             CLR  STP_BIT
             CLR  OBS_BIT
             CLR  MET_BIT
             RET
```

Intelligent Robot

```
REV_NOT:      CJNE A,#"4",LEF_NOT
               CLR  TEMP_BIT
               CLR  FORW_BIT
               CLR  REV_BIT
               SETB LEF_BIT
               CLR  RIG_BIT
               CLR  STP_BIT
               CLR  OBS_BIT
               CLR  MET_BIT
               RET
```

```
LEF_NOT:      CJNE A,#"6",RIG_NOT
               CLR  TEMP_BIT
               CLR  FORW_BIT
               CLR  REV_BIT
               CLR  LEF_BIT
               SETB RIG_BIT
               CLR  STP_BIT
               CLR  OBS_BIT
               CLR  MET_BIT
               RET
```

```
RIG_NOT:      CJNE A,#"5",STP_NOT
               CLR  TEMP_BIT
               CLR  FORW_BIT
               CLR  REV_BIT
               CLR  LEF_BIT
               CLR  RIG_BIT
               SETB STP_BIT
               CLR  OBS_BIT
               CLR  MET_BIT
               RET
```

```
STP_NOT:      CJNE A,#"T",TEMP_NOT
               SETB TEMP_BIT
               CLR  FORW_BIT
               CLR  REV_BIT
               CLR  LEF_BIT
               CLR  RIG_BIT
               CLR  STP_BIT
               CLR  OBS_BIT
               CLR  MET_BIT
```

```
TEMP_NOT:     RET
```

Intelligent Robot

/*-----Subroutine for LCD Initialization-----*/

```
LCD_INIT:      MOV  A,#30H
                CALL LCD_CMD_OUT
                CALL DELAY50MS

                MOV  A,#30H
                CALL LCD_CMD_OUT
                CALL DELAY50MS

                MOV  A,#38H
                CALL LCD_CMD_OUT

                MOV  A,#01H
                CALL LCD_CMD_OUT

                MOV  A,#06H
                CALL LCD_CMD_OUT

                MOV  A,#0CH
                CALL LCD_CMD_OUT
                RET
```

```
LCD_CLEAR:    MOV  A,#01H
                CALL LCD_CMD_OUT

                MOV  A,#80H
                CALL LCD_CMD_OUT
                RET
```

/*-----Initialization for Lines-----*/

```
DISPLINE1:    MOV  A,#80H
                CALL LCD_CMD_OUT
                RET

DISPLINE2:    MOV  A,#0C0H
                CALL LCD_CMD_OUT
                RET

DISPLINE3:    MOV  A,#94H
                CALL LCD_CMD_OUT
                RET

DISPLINE4:    MOV  A,#0D4H
                CALL LCD_CMD_OUT
                RET
```

Intelligent Robot

/*-----LCD Command Subroutine-----*/

```
LCD_CMD_OUT:  CALL BUSY_CHK
               MOV  LCD_PORT,A
               CLR  LCD_RS
               CLR  LCD_RW
               SETB LCD_EN
               NOP
               NOP
               CLR  LCD_EN
               RET
```

/*-----LCD Data Subroutine-----*/

```
LCD_DATA_OUT: CALL BUSY_CHK
               MOV  LCD_PORT,A
               SETB LCD_RS
               CLR  LCD_RW
               SETB LCD_EN
               NOP
               NOP
               CLR  LCD_EN
               RET
```

/*-----LCD Busy Check Subroutine-----*/

```
BUSY_CHK:     MOV  LCD_PORT,#0FFH
               CLR  LCD_RS
               SETB LCD_RW
BUSY_WAIT:    CLR  LCD_EN
               NOP
               NOP
               SETB LCD_EN
               NOP
               JB   LCD_PORT.7,BUSY_WAIT
               RET
```

```
WELCOME_NOTE: CALL DISPLINE1
               MOV  DPTR,#MYNAME1
               CALL DISP_LCD

               CALL DISPLINE2
               MOV  DPTR,#MYNAME2
               CALL DISP_LCD

               CALL DISPLINE3
               MOV  DPTR,#MYNAME3
```

Intelligent Robot

```
CALL DISP_LCD
```

```
CALL DISPLINE4  
MOV DPTR,#MYNAME4  
CALL DISP_LCD  
RET
```

```
/*-----Robot Movement Sequences and Displays-----*/
```

```
FORWARD:      CALL LCD_CLEAR  
              MOV DPTR,#FORW_STR  
              CALL DISP_LCD  
              MOV DPTR,#FORW_STR  
              CALL BT_TX  
              Setb FrLEDrt  
              Setb FrLEDlt  
              Clr  BkLEDrt  
              Clr  BkLEDlt  
              MOV A,#88H  
              MOV R2,A  
CONT_FORW:    MOV A,R2  
              MOV MOTOR_PORT,A  
              CALL LATCH_EN  
              RR   A  
              MOV R2,A  
              CALL DELAY50MS  
              JB   FORW_BIT,CONT_FORW  
              RET  
REVERSE:     CALL LCD_CLEAR  
              MOV DPTR,#REV_STR  
              CALL DISP_LCD  
              MOV DPTR,#REV_STR  
              CALL BT_TX  
              Clr  FrLEDrt  
              Clr  FrLEDlt  
              Setb BkLEDrt  
              Setb BkLEDlt  
              MOV A,#11H  
              MOV R2,A  
CONT_REV:    MOV A,R2  
              MOV MOTOR_PORT,A  
              CALL LATCH_EN  
              RL   A  
              MOV R2,A  
              CALL DELAY50MS  
              JB   REV_BIT,CONT_REV  
              RET
```

Intelligent Robot

```
LEFT:          CALL LCD_CLEAR
               MOV DPTR,#LEFT_STR
               CALL DISP_LCD
               MOV DPTR,#LEFT_STR
               CALL BT_TX
               Clr  FrLEDrt
               Setb FrLEDlt
               Clr  BkLEDrt
               Setb BkLEDlt

RLD_LEFT:     MOV DPTR,#LEFT2
CONT_LEF:     CLR  A
               MOVC   A,@A+DPTR
               JZ    RLD_LEFT
               MOV  MOTOR_PORT,A
               CALL LATCH_EN
               CALL DELAY50MS
               INC  DPTR
               JB   LEF_BIT,CONT_LEF
               RET

RIGHT:        CALL LCD_CLEAR
               MOV DPTR,#RIGHT_STR
               CALL DISP_LCD
               MOV DPTR,#RIGHT_STR
               CALL BT_TX
               Setb FrLEDrt
               Clr  FrLEDlt
               Setb BkLEDrt
               Clr  BkLEDlt

RLD_RIGHT:   MOV DPTR,#RIGHT2
CONT_RIG:    CLR  A
               MOVC   A,@A+DPTR
               JZ    RLD_RIGHT
               MOV  MOTOR_PORT,A
               CALL LATCH_EN
               CALL DELAY50MS
               INC  DPTR
               JB   RIG_BIT,CONT_RIG
               RET

STOP:        CALL LCD_CLEAR
               MOV DPTR,#STOP_STR
               CALL DISP_LCD
               MOV DPTR,#STOP_STR
               CALL BT_TX
```

Intelligent Robot

```
CALL DELAY1Sec
MOV MOTOR_PORT,#00H
CALL LATCH_EN
RET
```

```
LATCH_EN:    CLR  MOTOR_EN
             NOP
             NOP
             NOP
             SETB MOTOR_EN
             RET
```

/*-----Blue Tooth Device Subroutine For connection-----*/

```
BT_INIT:    SETB BT_MODE
LINK_CHK:   MOV  R0,#30H
            MOV  DPTR,#ATEN
            CALL BT_TX
            CALL DELAY1Sec

            MOV  R0,#32H
            MOV  A,@R0
            CJNE A,#"O",LINK_FAIL
            INC  R0
            MOV  A,@R0
            CJNE A,#"K",LINK_FAIL

            CALL LCD_CLEAR
            CALL DISPLINE1
            MOV  DPTR,#LINK_OK
            CALL DISP_LCD
            JMP  CONT_BT

LINK_FAIL:  CALL DISPLINE3
            MOV  DPTR,#NO_LINK
            CALL DISP_LCD
            JMP  LINK_CHK

CONT_BT:    MOV  DPTR,#SREST
            CALL BT_TX
            CALL DELAY1Sec

            MOV  DPTR,#HREST
            CALL BT_TX
            CALL DELAY1Sec
```

Intelligent Robot

```
MOV DPTR,#HREST
CALL BT_TX
CALL DELAY1Sec
```

```
MOV DPTR,#MODE
CALL BT_TX
CALL DELAY1Sec
CALL DELAY1Sec
```

```
MOV DPTR,#INFO
MOV R0,#30H
CALL BT_TX
```

```
CALL DELAY1Sec
CALL DELAY1Sec
CALL FIND_ID
```

```
CALL DELAY1Sec
CALL DELAY1Sec
CALL DELAY1Sec
CALL DELAY1Sec
```

```
MOV DPTR,#Dial
CALL BT_TX
CALL DELAY1Sec
CALL RX_CLR
```

```
CHECK_AGAIN: MOV R0,#30H
CALL DELAY1Sec
CALL DELAY1Sec
MOV R0,#32H
MOV A,@R0
CJNE A,#43H,NO_CONN
CLR BT_MODE
RET
```

```
NO_CONN: CALL LCD_CLEAR
CALL DISPLINE2
MOV DPTR,#NTCON
CALL DISP_LCD
JMP CHECK_AGAIN
```

```
RX_CLR: MOV R0,#30H
RX_RAMCLR: CLR A
MOV @R0,A
INC R0
CJNE R0,#6FH,RX_RAMCLR
```

Intelligent Robot

```
MOV R0,#30H
RET
```

/*-----Transmission of Command with Delay-----*/

```
BT_TX:      Clr  FBTxOk
NXT_TX:     CLR  A
            MOVC  A,@A+DPTR
            JZ   EXIT_TX
            MOV  SBUF,A
            JNB  FBTxOk,$
            NOP
            Clr  FBTxOk
            INC  DPTR
            SJMP NXT_TX
EXIT_TX:    RET
```

/*-----Slave Device Address-----*/

```
FIND_ID:    CALL LCD_CLEAR
            CALL DISPLINE1
            MOV  R0,#32H
NXT_ID:     MOV  A,@R0
            INC  R0
            CJNE A,#2CH,CONT_ID      ;2CH stands for ASCII value
            CALL DISPLINE2
NXT_VER:    MOV  A,@R0
            INC  R0
            CJNE A,#2CH,CONT_VER     ; comma (,)
            CALL DISPLINE3
NXT_MOD:    MOV  A,@R0
            INC  R0
            CJNE A,#2CH,CONT_MODE
            CALL DISPLINE4
NXT_STTS:   MOV  A,@R0
            INC  R0
            CJNE A,#0DH,CONT_STTS    ;This checking is for carriage
                                     return
            RET
CONT_ID:    CALL LCD_DATA_OUT
            JMP  NXT_ID
CONT_VER:   CALL LCD_DATA_OUT
            JMP  NXT_VER
CONT_MODE:  CALL LCD_DATA_OUT
            JMP  NXT_MOD
CONT_STTS:  CALL LCD_DATA_OUT
```

Intelligent Robot

```
DISP_LCD:    JMP  NXT_STTS
             CLR  A
             MOVC A,@A+DPTR
             JZ   DISP_OUT
             CALL LCD_DATA_OUT
             INC  DPTR
             SJMP DISP_LCD
DISP_OUT:    RET
```

/*-----Obstacle Subroutine Program-----*/

```
OBS_Detect:  MOV  MOTOR_PORT,#00H
             CALL LATCH_EN
             CALL LCD_CLEAR
             MOV  DPTR,#OBS_STR
             CALL DISP_LCD
             MOV  DPTR,#OBS_STR
             Clr  FBTxOk
             CALL BT_TX
             RET
```

```
OBS_ISR:    SETB OBS_BIT
             CLR  MET_BIT
             CLR  FORW_BIT
             CLR  REV_BIT
             CLR  LEF_BIT
             CLR  RIG_BIT
             CLR  STP_BIT
             CLR  TEMP_BIT
             RET
```

/*-----Smoke Detection Program-----*/

```
TIMER0_ISR: CLR  TR0
             CLR  TF0
             MOV  TH0,#4BH
             MOV  TL0,#0FCH
             JNB  SMOKE_BIT,SMOKE_ALARM
             SETB TR0
             RET
```

```
SMOKE_ALARM: SETB SMOKE_BIT
             SETB GAS_BIT
             CLR  MET_BIT
             CLR  OBS_BIT
             CLR  FORW_BIT
             CLR  REV_BIT
```

Intelligent Robot

```
CLR  LEF_BIT
CLR  RIG_BIT
CLR  STP_BIT
CLR  TEMP_BIT
CLR  BT_MODE
RET
```

```
Smoke_Detect:  Mov  Motor_Port,#00h
                Call  Latch_EN
                Mov   Dptr,#Smoke_Str
                Call  Disp_LCD
                Mov   Dptr,#Smoke_Str
                Call  BT_TX
                CALL  DELAY1SEC
                SETB  TR0
                RET
```

/*-----Metal Detection Subroutine Program-----*/

```
MET_ISR:       SETB  MET_BIT
                CLR   OBS_BIT
                CLR   FORW_BIT
                CLR   REV_BIT
                CLR   LEF_BIT
                CLR   RIG_BIT
                CLR   STP_BIT
                CLR   TEMP_BIT
                CLR   BT_MODE
                RET
```

```
Metal_Detect:  MOV   MOTOR_PORT,#00H
                CALL  LATCH_EN
                CALL  LCD_CLEAR
                MOV   DPTR,#MET_STR
                CALL  DISP_LCD
                MOV   DPTR,#MET_STR
                Clr   FBTxOk
                CALL  BT_TX
                RET
```

/*-----Serial Communication Interfacing program-----*/

```
SRL_ISR:      JBC   TI,TX_LOOP
                JBC   RI,RX_LOOP
```

```
TX_LOOP:     SETB  FBTxOk
                RET
```

Intelligent Robot

```
RX_LOOP:      MOV  A,SBUF
              JB   BT_MODE,BT_REC
              MOV  R7,A
              CALL SET_DIR
              RET
```

```
BT_REC:       MOV  @R0,A
              INC  R0
              RET
```

/*-----Subroutine for Initializing Temperature Sensor DS 1631-----*/

```
TEMP_INIT:    CALL START_TEMP
              MOV  A,#CNTR_WRD_WRITE
              CALL TEMP_SEND

              MOV  A,#STOP_CONV
              CALL TEMP_SEND
              CALL STOP_TEMP

              CALL START_TEMP
              MOV  A,#CNTR_WRD_WRITE
              CALL TEMP_SEND

              MOV  A,#ACCESS_CONFIG
              CALL TEMP_SEND

              MOV  A,#CNTR_WRD_WRITE
              CALL TEMP_SEND

              MOV  A,#CONFIG_REG
              CALL TEMP_SEND
              CALL STOP_TEMP

              CALL START_TEMP
              MOV  A,#CNTR_WRD_WRITE
              CALL TEMP_SEND

              MOV  A,#ACCESS_TH
              CALL TEMP_SEND

              MOV  A,#CNTR_WRD_WRITE
              CALL TEMP_SEND

              MOV  A,#MAX_TEMP
```

Intelligent Robot

```
CALL TEMP_SEND

MOV A,#00H
CALL TEMP_SEND
CALL STOP_TEMP

CALL START_TEMP
MOV A,#CNTR_WRD_WRITE
CALL TEMP_SEND

MOV A,#ACCESS_TL
CALL TEMP_SEND

MOV A,#CNTR_WRD_WRITE
CALL TEMP_SEND

MOV A,#MIN_TEMP
CALL TEMP_SEND

MOV A,#00H
CALL TEMP_SEND
CALL STOP_TEMP
RET
```

```
READ_TEMP: CALL TEMP_INIT
MOV MOTOR_PORT,#00H
CALL LATCH_EN

CALL START_TEMP
MOV A,#CNTR_WRD_WRITE
CALL TEMP_SEND

MOV A,#StartConv
CALL TEMP_SEND
CALL STOP_TEMP

CALL DELAY1SEC

CALL START_TEMP
MOV A,#CNTR_WRD_WRITE
CALL TEMP_SEND

MOV A,#STOP_CONV
CALL TEMP_SEND
CALL STOP_TEMP
```

Intelligent Robot

```
CALL START_TEMP
MOV A,#CNTR_WRD_WRITE
CALL TEMP_SEND
```

```
MOV A,#Read_Tempr
CALL TEMP_SEND
CALL STOP_TEMP
```

```
CALL START_TEMP
MOV A,#CNTR_WRD_READ
CALL TEMP_SEND
```

```
CALL TEMP_READ
CALL MASTER_ACK
MOV TEMP_MSB,A
```

```
CALL TEMP_READ
CALL MASTER_NACK
```

```
CALL STOP_TEMP
MOV TEMP_LSB,A
```

```
CALL CONV_ASCII
RET
```

```
TEMP_READ: CLR A
MOV R3,#08H
NXT_READ: SETB Tempr_SCL
MOV C,Tempr_SDA
CALL DELAY5USEC
CLR Tempr_SCL
RLC A
CLR C
CALL DELAY5USEC
DJNZ R3,NXT_READ
RET
```

```
MASTER_ACK: CLR Tempr_SCL
NOP
CLR Tempr_SDA
CALL DELAY5USEC
SETB Tempr_SCL
CALL DELAY50MS
CLR Tempr_SCL
CALL DELAY5USEC
SETB Tempr_SDA
NOP
```

Intelligent Robot

NOP
RET

MASTER_NACK: CLR Tempr_SCL
CALL DELAY5USEC
SETB Tempr_SDA
CALL DELAY5USEC
SETB Tempr_SCL
CALL DELAY5USEC
CLR Tempr_SCL
CALL DELAY5USEC
CLR Tempr_SDA
RET

TEMP_SEND: MOV R3,#08H

SEND_NXT: CLR C
RLC A
MOV TEMPR_SDA,C
NOP
SETB Tempr_SCL

CALL DELAY5USEC
CLR Tempr_SCL
DJNZ R3,SEND_NXT

CALL DELAY5USEC
SETB Tempr_SDA
CALL DELAY5USEC
SETB Tempr_SCL

CALL DELAY50MS
CALL DELAY50MS
CALL DELAY50MS
CLR Tempr_SCL
CALL DELAY5USEC
SETB Tempr_SDA
RET

STOP_TEMP: CLR Tempr_SCL
CALL DELAY5USEC
CLR Tempr_SDA
SETB Tempr_SCL
CALL DELAY50MS
SETB Tempr_SDA
NOP

Intelligent Robot

```
    NOP
    RET
```

```
START_TEMP:  SETB  Tempr_SDA
              CALL DELAY5USEC
              SETB  Tempr_SCL
              CLR   Tempr_SDA
              CALL DELAY5USEC
              CLR   Tempr_SCL
              NOP
              RET
```

```
DELAY5USEC:  NOP
              NOP
              NOP
              NOP
              RET
```

```
DISPLAY_TEMP: CALL LCD_CLEAR
               CALL DISPLINE4
               MOV  DPTR,#TEMP_STAT
               CALL DISP_LCD

               MOV  DPTR,#TEMP_STAT
               CALL BT_TX
               MOV  A,TEMP_3
               CALL LCD_DATA_OUT

               MOV  SBUF,A
               CALL DELAY10MS
               MOV  A,TEMP_2
               CALL LCD_DATA_OUT

               MOV  SBUF,A
               CALL DELAY10MS
               MOV  A,TEMP_1
               CALL LCD_DATA_OUT

               MOV  SBUF,A
               CALL DELAY10MS
               MOV  DPTR,#FLOAT_TEMP
               MOV  A,TEMP_LSB
               MOV  B,#05H
               SWAP A
               ANL  A,#0FH
               MUL  AB
               ADD  A,DPL
```

Intelligent Robot

```
JNC  CONT_LSB  
INC  DPH
```

```
CONT_LSB:  MOV  DPL,A  
           MOV  R3,#05H  
NXT_LSB:   CLR  A  
           MOVC  A,@A+DPTR  
           CALL LCD_DATA_OUT  
           MOV  SBUF,A  
           CALL DELAY10MS  
           INC  DPTR  
           DJNZ R3,NXT_LSB  
  
           MOV  DPTR,#DEGR_C  
           CALL DISP_LCD  
           MOV  DPTR,#DEGR_C  
           CALL BT_TX  
           RET
```

```
/*-----Given a Hex number, Convert that into decimal magnitude */  
/*----- again convert each digit into ASCII code-----*/
```

```
CONV_ASCII:  MOV  R1,#70H  
            MOV  A,Temp_MSB  
            MOV  B,#10  
            DIV  AB  
            MOV  @R1,B  
            INC  R1  
            MOV  B,#10  
            DIV  AB  
            MOV  @R1,B  
            INC  R1  
            MOV  @R1,A  
  
            MOV  R4,#03H  
            MOV  R1,#70H  
Cont_Aski:  MOV  A,@R1  
            ORL  A,#30H  
            MOV  @R1,A  
            INC  R1  
            Djnz R4,Cont_Aski  
            RET
```

```
/*-----Delay Subroutines-----*/
```

```
DELAY5SEC:  MOV  DelayC3,#50  
            CALL DLY_1S
```

Intelligent Robot

RET

```
DELAY1SEC:  MOV DelayC3,#10
DLY_1S:     MOV DelayC2,#200
DLY_500US:  MOV DelayC1,#230
            DJNZ DelayC1,$
            DJNZ DelayC2,DLY_500US
            DJNZ DelayC3,DLY_1S
            RET
```

```
DELAY50MS:  MOV DelayC3,#01H
            MOV DelayC2,#100
            CALL DLY_500US
            RET
```

```
DELAY10MS:  MOV DelayC3,#01H
            MOV DelayC2,#20
            CALL DLY_500US
            RET
```

/*-----Display Commands-----*/

```
Forw1:      DB 88h,22h,44h,11h,00h
Rev1:       DB 11H, 44H,22H,88H,00H
LEFT2:      DB 81h,42h,24h,18h,00h
RIGHT2:     DB 18h,24h,42h,81h,00h

MYNAME1:    DB "Manu, Prasad, Mahipal",0
MYNAME2:    DB "Srinivas Sir (GUIDE)",0
MYNAME3:    DB "PIRMEC Students",0
MYNAME4:    DB "BT ROBO PROJECT ",0

FORW_STR:   DB "Moving Forward",0DH,0AH,0
REV_STR:    DB "Moving Reverse",0DH,0AH,0
LEFT_STR:   DB "Taking Left Turn ",0DH,0AH,0
RIGHT_STR:  DB "Taking Right Right",0DH,0AH,0
STOP_STR:   DB "ROBO STOPPED",0DH,0AH,0

ATEN:       DB "AT",0DH,0
SREST:      DB "ATZ",0DH,0
HREST:      DB "AT&F",0DH,0
MODE:       DB "AT+BTMODE0",0DH,0
INFO:       DB "AT+BTINFO?",0DH,0
DIAL:       DB "ATD00019505FF5D",0DH,0

NTCON:      DB "BT Not Connected",0
NO_LINK:    DB "BT Link Failed",0
```

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```
LINK_OK:   DB   "BT Link O K ",0

SND_ROT:   DB   "Please Send Commands for Movement",0DH,0AH,
            "8- Forward",0DH,0AH,
            "2-Reverse",0DH,0AH,
            "4-Left",0DH,0AH,
            "6-Right",0DH,0AH,
            "5-Stopping Robot",0DH,0AH,0

CONN_OK:   DB   "Connected To Master", 0

OBS_STR:   DB   "*Obstacle Detected*", 0DH, 0AH, 0

MET_STR:   DB   "Metal Found ", 0DH, 0AH, 0

Smoke_Str: DB   "L P G Gas Found.... ", 0DH,0AH,0

TEMPR:     DB   "Press (T) For Reading Temperature", 0DH, 0AH,0
TEMP_STAT: DB   "Temp: ", 0
DEGR_C:    DB   "°C", 0DH, 0AH, 0
```

FLOAT_TEMP:

```
DB ".0000"
DB ".0625"
DB ".1250"
DB ".1875"
DB ".2500"
DB ".3125"
DB ".3750"
DB ".4375"
DB ".5000"
DB ".5625"
DB ".6250"
DB ".6875"
DB ".7500"
DB ".8125"
DB ".8750"
DB ".9375"           ; max 5 bytes
```

END

14. Conclusion & Future scopes

Conclusion:

- The Bluetooth communication was observed in the range of 30mts.
- The movement of Robo was observed and the delay can be adjusted as per the user requirement.
- Metal was detected within range of 4-5 cms (max)
- Obstacle was detected within the range of 10cms.
- Inflammable gas was detected (Gas sensor checks gas for every 50ms).
- Temperature was detected with a resolution of 0.5°C.

Future Scopes:

- Infrared sensor can be replaced by infrared camera.
- Metal sensor can be replaced by High capacity sensors.
- High capacity motors can be used to move the robo faster.
- Robo can also equipped with rechargeable batteries increasing efficiency and reducing labor.

Intelligent Robot

References:

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- 8051 Microcontroller and Embedded systems using assembly & C by Muhammad Ali Mazdi.
- Bluetooth – Connect without cables by Jennifer Bray and Charles F. Sturman

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